

D7.4 DEFINED SCENARIOS AND DATA INVENTORIES FOR FINAL SUSTAINABILITY ASSESSMENT WORK PACKAGE 7

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T7.2 Mass and energy balances

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

History Log.....	1
Quality Review	1
TABLE OF CONTENTS	3
LIST OF FIGURES.....	5
LIST OF TABLES.....	7
Publishable executive summary.....	9
Abbreviations	11
1. Introduction	13
2. Scenario definition and process flow schemes.....	14
2.1. Scenario definition	14
2.1.1. Innovative scenarios and baseline scenario for household plastic packaging waste	17
2.1.2. Innovative scenario and baseline scenario for business plastic packaging waste ...	21
2.2. Process flow schemes.....	23
2.2.1. Innovative scenarios	24
2.2.2. Baseline scenarios	31
2.2.3. Collection, Sorting and Pretreatment.....	35
2.2.4. Purification option A CreaSolv®	36
2.2.5. Purification option B Delamination and Deinking.....	37
2.2.1. Post-treatment Recompounding	38
2.2.2. Post-treatment Deodorization	39
2.2.3. Laminate production.....	39
2.2.4. Tracer production	44
2.2.5. Ink, Primer and Heat protective lacquer production	44
2.2.6. Food and non-food packaging production	46
3. Data Inventories.....	47
3.1. Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) data collection	47
3.2. Life Cycle Costing (LCC) data collection	48
3.3. Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA) data collection	50
4. Conclusion	54
5. Bibliography.....	57
Annex	59
Collection and SoA sorting and Pretreatment-SUEZ.....	62

Purification option A CreaSolv®-IVV.....	68
Purification option B Delamination and Deinking-UGENT.....	70
Recompounding-SUEZ.....	72
Deodorization-KREYEN.....	74
Laminate production-AMCOR.....	77
Tracer production-POLY.....	82
Ink, Primer and heat protective lacquer production-Siegwerk.....	84
Food and non-food packaging production-Nestle/Mespack.....	88

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1: Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment (LCSA) definition adapted from Kloepffer (2008)	13
Figure 2: Overview of main innovative and baseline scenarios for household waste within the system perspective, S3.....	19
Figure 3: Visualisation of the basket of products approach used in case of the system perspective for household waste, Scenarios S1, S2, S3.....	20
Figure 4: Visualisation of the approach used in case of the material perspective for household waste, Scenarios M1, M2, M3, rPE: recycled PE, vPE: virgin PE.....	21
Figure 5 Overview of EOL scenarios for PE-rich business flexible packaging waste, S4, S5.....	22
Figure 6: Visualisation of the basket of product approach used for the system perspective for business waste, Scenarios S4, S5.....	23
Figure 7: Overview of the (S1) NF packaging from household waste (Loop 1) process flow scheme for the system perspective	25
Figure 8: Foreground system boundary and involved processes of (S1) NF packaging from household waste (Loop 1) for the system perspective; OPV: heat protective lacquer.....	26
Figure 9: Overview of the (S2) F and NF packaging from household waste – (Loop 3 cycle 1-2 and Loop 1) process flow scheme for the system perspective, The processes highlighted with a grey box pertain specifically to Loop 1, while those highlighted with a light green box in the foreground system are specific to Loop 3.	27
Figure 10: Foreground system boundary and involved processes of (S2) F and NF packaging from household waste – (Loop 3 cycle 1-2 and Loop 1) for the system perspective; OPV: heat protective lacquer.....	28
Figure 11: Overview of the (S4) F packaging from business waste (Loop 2) flow scheme for the system perspective.....	29
Figure 12: Foreground system boundary and involved processes of Business, F packaging scenario - Loop 2 for the system perspective; OPV: heat protective lacquer	30
Figure 13: (M1) NF pellet scenario - Loop 1 process flow scheme for the material perspective.....	30
Figure 14: (M2) F pellet scenario - Loop 3 process flow scheme for the material perspective	31
Figure 15: Baseline scenario (S3) process flow scheme for the household waste scenarios of system perspective.....	33
Figure 16: Baseline scenario (S5) process flow scheme for the business waste scenario	34
Figure 17: Baseline pellet scenario process flow scheme for the virgin PE pellet production of the material perspective	35
Figure 18: Loop 1 Collection and SoA sorting and Pretreatment process flow scheme	35
Figure 19: Loop 2 Collection and Pretreatment process flow scheme.....	36
Figure 20: Loop 3 Collection and SoA sorting and Pretreatment process flow scheme	36
Figure 21: Loops 1 Purification option A CreaSolv [®] process flow scheme.....	37
Figure 22: Loop 2 Purification option B Delamination and Deinking process flow scheme	37
Figure 23: Loop 3 Purification option B Delamination and Deinking process flow scheme	38
Figure 24: Loop 2 and 3 Recompounding process flow scheme	38
Figure 25 Loop 1 Deodorization process flow scheme	39
Figure 26: Loop 2 and 3 Deodorization process flow scheme.....	39
Figure 27: Loop 1 NF scenario- Detergent tabs (HP2) laminate production process flow scheme... ..	40

Figure 28: Loop 2 F scenario- Coffee (FP2) laminate production process flow scheme	40
Figure 29: Loop 3 F scenario- Coffee (FP2) laminate production process flow scheme	41
Figure 30: Loop 1-3 Baseline scenario- MuMu laminate (NF and F) production process flow scheme	42
Figure 31: Loop 1 Baseline scenario- MuMu laminate (NF) production process flow scheme	42
Figure 32 Loop 1 Baseline scenario- MoMu laminate (NF) production process flow scheme	43
Figure 33: Loop 3 Baseline scenario- MoMu laminate (F) production process flow scheme	43
Figure 34: Loop 3 Tracer production process flow scheme	44
Figure 35: Loops 1-2 Ink production process flow scheme	45
Figure 36: Loop 3 Ink production process flow scheme	45
Figure 37: Loops 2-3 Primer production process flow scheme	46
Figure 38: Loops 1-3 Heat protective lacquer production process flow scheme	46
Figure 39: Loops 1-3 Food and non-food packaging production process flow scheme	46

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1: Definition of innovative cases to provide food and non-food packaging	15
Table 2: Innovative and baseline scenarios for both the system and the material perspectives. For the innovative scenarios including their purification pathways and demonstrators assessed in this study, NA: non-applicable	16
Table 3: Involved partners per process step	23
Table 4: Example of Data collection template for Life Cycle Assessment (LCA)	48
Table 5: Data collection template for Life Cycle Costing (LCC)	49
Table 6: Data collection template for Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA) part 1 (infobox).....	50
Table 7: Living Wage Categories 2023 additional information for the indicator Percentage of workers who are paid a living wage or above for Germany, France, Belgium and Switzerland	53
Table 8: Key aspects requiring attention regarding data requirements and confidential data; this list is not exhaustive, but captures the primary areas of concern.....	56
Table 9: Data collection template for Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA) part 2 (data inventory) 59	
Table 10: Loop 1 Collection and SoA sorting and Pretreatment data inventory sheet.....	63
Table 11: Loop 2 Collection data inventory sheet	64
Table 12: Loop 2 Pretreatment data inventory sheet	64
Table 13: Loop 3 Collection and SoA sorting and Pretreatment data inventory sheet	65
Table 14: LCC data inventory SoA sorting SUEZ, sce. = service, pc. = piece	66
Table 15: LCC data inventory Pretreatment SUEZ	67
Table 16: Loops 1-3 Purification option A CreaSolv® data inventory sheet (data on solvent is confidential)	68
Table 17: LCC data inventory Purification option A CreaSolv® IVV	69
Table 18: LCC data inventory Purification option B Delamination and Deinking UGENT	71
Table 19: Loop 2-3 Recompounding data inventory sheet	72
Table 20: LCC data inventory Recompounding SUEZ	73
Table 21: Loop 1 Deodorization data inventory sheet, confidential process engineering data e.g. air for cooling	74
Table 22: Loop 2-3 Deodorization data inventory sheet, confidential process engineering data e.g. air for cooling	74
Table 23: LCC data inventory Deodorization KREYEN	75
Table 24: S-LCA data inventory Deodorization KREYEN	76
Table 25: Loop 1 Detergent Tabs Laminate production data inventory sheet (confidential energy data).....	77
Table 26: Loop 2-3 F scenario- Coffee (FP2) Laminate production data inventory sheet.....	78
Table 27: LCC data inventory AMCOR, SiOx missing, OPV i.e. heat protective lacquer missing, triplex, duplex differences in price missing	79
Table 28: S-LCA data inventory AMCORG = AMCOR Ghent, safety training numbers to be updated, N/A not available, n.a. not applicable	80
Table 29: S-LCA data inventory AMCORK, = AMCOR Kreuzlingen, non-fatal accidents to be clarified	81
Table 30: S-LCA data inventory POLY	83
Table 31: Loop 1-2 Ink CMYK production data inventory sheet; K: black	84

Table 32: Loops 1-2 Ink white production data inventory sheet	84
Table 33: Loop 3 Ink CMYK production data inventory sheet, data on tracer is confidential, K= black	85
Table 34: Loop 3 Ink + tracer white production data inventory sheet, data on tracer is confidential	85
Table 35: Loop 2-3 Primer production data inventory sheet	85
Table 36: Loop -3 Heat protective lacquer inventory sheet.....	86
Table 37: S-LCA data inventory Siegwark	87
Table 38: Loop 2-3 Food packaging production data inventory sheet, tbd: to be disclosed, N/A not applicable, losses are not evaluated per step but at the beginning included in the folding process	88
Table 39: S-LCA data inventory NESTLÉ	89

PUBLISHABLE EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

In the CIRCULAR FoodPack project, the newly developed value chains from WP2 and WP3 undergo a comprehensive life cycle sustainability assessment (LCSA), which integrates environmental impacts through Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), economic impacts through Life Cycle Costing (LCC), and social impacts through Social LCA (S-LCA).

Within the framework of life cycle thinking, four phases are essential for conducting these assessments: a) goal and scope definition phase, b) inventory analysis phase, c) impact assessment phase, and d) interpretation phase (ISO 14044, 2006).

Until M30, the primary focus was on achieving milestone 13 by enhancing the innovative and baseline scenarios, ensuring consistent process flow schemes for the final sustainability assessment. This involved refining the scenarios based on the three use cases (Loops 1-3) that generate home packaging (H), personal care packaging (PC), and food packaging (F), encompassing the following five demonstrators/applications: Wet wipes (H1), Detergent tabs (H2), Cosmetics in sachets (PC1), Chocolate powder (F1), and Coffee (F2). The Loops represent different feasible process cascades experimented in the CFP project, which are then translated into scenarios for the LCSA model. A distinction is drawn between innovative scenarios for household and business waste, each with the corresponding baseline scenarios. Additionally, two different perspectives are considered, including (i) system perspective, focusing on packaging applications; and (ii) material perspective focusing on pellet specifications. From the system perspective (S¹), the final assessment comprises three main innovative scenarios, one sub-scenario and two baseline scenarios tailored to both household or business waste. Specifically for household waste, these scenarios include: (S1) Non-food (NF) packaging from household waste (Loop 1), (S2) Food (F) and NF packaging from household waste – (Loop 3 cycle 1 and Loop 1), sub-scenario (S2.1) F and NF packaging from household waste – (Loop 3 cycle 2 and Loop 1) and (S3) Baseline for household waste. For business waste, the scenarios consist of: (S4) F packaging from business waste (Loop 2), and (S5) Baseline for business waste. In terms of the material perspective (M²), three primary scenarios are explored for household waste input: (M1) NF pellet scenario - Loop 1, (M2) F pellet scenario - Loop 3, and (M3) Baseline pellet scenario, resulting in the production of either recycled PE (rPE) pellets or virgin PE (vPE) pellets in the Baseline scenario.

Another substantial aspect involved collaboratively refining process flow schemes with project partners for the following processes:

- (1) Collection, state of the art (SoA) sorting and tracer-based sorting,
- (2) Pretreatment including oversorting, shredding, washing, grinding and float-sink separation,
- (3) Purification with option A-CreaSolv® and option B-deinking and delamination,
- (4) Posttreatment consisting of recompounding and deodorization,
- (5) Laminate production and also considering ink production, primer production and tracer production and
- (6) Food and non-food packaging production.

Particular attention was directed towards the Business, F packaging scenario (Loop 2), including the Business to Business (B2B) collection, pretreatment, and the baseline scenario, as well as to

¹ The abbreviation "S" stands for system perspective scenario

² The abbreviation "M" represents material perspective scenario

delamination and deinking, laminate, and food and non-food packaging, due to the data gaps and updates resulting from process improvements during the project period.

Based on this collaborative effort, data for LCA, LCC, and S-LCA inventories have been supplemented by the respective partners to complete the necessary data for the final sustainability assessment.

ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	
B2B	Business to business
CAPEX	Capital expenditure
EoL	End of life
F	Food
FP	Food packaging
FU	Functional Unit
HP	Home packaging
IVV	Fraunhofer Institute IVV
KREYEN	Kreyenborg
LCA	Life cycle assessment
LCC	Life cycle costing
LCI	Life cycle inventory
LCSA	Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment
LDPE	Low-Density Polyethylene
LLDPE	Linear Low-Density Polyethylene
M	Material perspective scenario
MoMu	Mono-material multilayers
MuMu	Multi-material multilayers
n.a.	Not applicable
N/A	Not available
NF	Non-Food
OPEX	Operating expenditure
PE	Polyethylene
PCP	Personal care packaging
PCR	Post-consumer recyclates
POLY	Polysecure
rPE	Recycled PE
S	System perspective scenario
S-LCA	Social Life Cycle Assessment

SoA	State of the art
Tbd	To be discussed
TBS	Tracer Based Sorting
vPE	Virgin PE
WP	Work Package

1. INTRODUCTION

This deliverable outlines further developments based on the project progress following the initial phase of Work Package 7 (WP7: Comprehensive Sustainability Assessment and Decision-support Tool). Specifically, it encompasses the implementations, refinements, and iterations of the scenario definition and process flow schemes (Task 7.1) and the mass and energy balances (Task 7.2).

WP7 aims to conduct a comprehensive assessment of the sustainability of newly developed value chains, incorporating new technology and packaging design. This assessment is carried out systematically, considering the entire life cycle and holistically addressing environmental, economic, and social impacts. Life cycle assessment (LCA), life cycle costing (LCC), and social life cycle assessment (S-LCA), which are part of the Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment (LCSA), as depicted in Figure 1, form the methodological foundation for evaluating the respective impacts (Kloepffer, 2008).

$$\text{LCSA} = \text{LCA} + \text{LCC} + \text{SLCA}$$

Figure 1: Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment (LCSA) definition adapted from Kloepffer (2008)

An LCA study comprises four phases: a) goal and scope definition, b) inventory analysis, c) impact assessment, and d) interpretation (ISO 14044, 2006). These phases provide the framework not only for LCA itself (ISO 14044, 2006) but also for the LCC modelling structure (Ciroth et al., 2011) and the S-LCA (Goedkoop et al., 2020; UNEP et al., 2020).

The current Deliverable 7.4 focuses on refining the scenarios in collaboration with technology and packaging developers, starting from three defined use cases (Loops 1-3) which are compared to the state of the art (SoA) baseline treatment scenarios i.e. incineration and landfilling.

These loops represent specific process cascades, which are used for the formulation of innovative scenarios. A differentiation is made between innovative scenarios for PE-rich household and business post-consumer flexible packaging waste, alongside their respective baseline scenarios. Furthermore, a distinction is drawn between the system perspective and the material perspective, evident in the area of application and the resulting material. In the former, the focus is on packaging, while in the latter, it shifts to the pellets.

From the system perspective, Loops representing different feasible process cascades experimented in the CFP project are partly combined, such as Loop 1 and Loop 3, into three main innovative scenarios and one innovative sub-scenario complemented by two baseline scenarios. For household waste these encompass: (S1) NF packaging from household waste (Loop 1), (S2) F and NF packaging

from household waste – (Loop 3 cycle 1 and Loop 1), sub-scenario (S2.1) F and NF packaging from household waste – (Loop 3 cycle 2 and Loop 1) and (S3) Baseline for household waste. For business waste, the scenarios consist of: (S4) F packaging from business waste (Loop 2), and (S5) Baseline for business waste. This combination is intended for the LCSA model according to the functional unit (FU).

From the material perspective, three main scenarios, namely (M1) NF pellet scenario - Loop 1, (M2) F pellet scenario - Loop 3, and (M3) Baseline pellet scenario, are considered for the household waste input.

Furthermore, the scope of Deliverable 7.4 includes refining the LCA and LCC data inventory, essential for the final sustainability assessment, along with the gathered S-LCA data. Consequently, partners completed the data collection templates (as depicted in Chapter Data Inventories and Annex), followed by refining data in bilateral meetings when updates were required.

2. SCENARIO DEFINITION AND PROCESS FLOW SCHEMES

The geographical focus of this study is Europe, as the composition of flexible packaging waste was analysed in three sorting plants in France, Belgium and Germany. These facilities are considered the state-of-the-art in sorting processes used in many EU countries. The timeframe of the evaluation covers the duration of the project (2021-2024). The study incorporates prospective elements, particularly technologies that are in the lab and pilot-scale testing phase rather than fully industrial operational. The scenarios are focusing on industrial implementation.

2.1. Scenario definition

Three primary process cascades, referred to as Loops (Table 1), are analysed in this project, each varying, for example, in the input of either mixed end-of-life (EoL) food (F) flexible and EoL non-food (NF) flexible, solely EoL- mono-material F flexible packaging waste or mixed EoL F (mono-material) and NF flexibles, with tracers in the F flexibles. The output of each Loop is a newly designed mono-material laminate³ comprising a blend of virgin polyethylene (PE⁴) and PE post-consumer-recyclates (PCRs). The project encompasses three categories of packaging applications: home packaging (HP), personal care packaging (PCP), and food packaging (FP). It includes the following five applications⁵:

1. Wet wipes (HP1)
2. Detergent tabs (HP2)
3. Cosmetics in sachets (PCP1)
4. Chocolate powder (FP1)
5. Coffee (FP2)

In the case of food applications (FP1 and FP2), functional barriers are incorporated to prevent unwanted migration from the recycle into the product. In Loop 3, which encompasses two product

³ Food packaging currently predominantly consists of multi-materials but is transitioning towards mono-material.

⁴ Low-Density Polyethylene (LDPE)/Linear Low-Density Polyethylene (LLDPE) is specifically focused on, but subsequently, the broader term PE or rPE will be utilized.

⁵ Creamer (FP3) was removed from the demonstrators due to the non-recyclability of small packaging since they are likely to be sorted out by wind sifting, as mentioned by project partners.

cycles as sub-scenarios, tracers are introduced into the laminate. For the final sustainability assessment, the focus will be on two applications: detergent tabs (HP2) and coffee (FP2). The rationale is elaborated further in this section.

Table 1: Definition of innovative cases to provide food and non-food packaging

Case	Input Origin	Input	Purification pathway	Output	Application under study
Loop 1	Household plastic packaging waste	Mixed - EoL F and NF flexibles	CreaSolv®	Laminate 1: mono-material with <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PE virgin • PE PCR from F and NF origin 	HP2: detergent tabs
Loop 2	Business plastic packaging waste	EoL F (mono-material) flexibles	Delamination and Deinking	Laminate 2: mono-material with <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PE virgin • PE PCR from F origin • Functional barriers 	FP2: Coffee
Loop 3 cycle 1	Household plastic packaging waste	Mixed – EoL F (mono-material) and NF flexibles, with tracers in the F flexibles	Delamination and Deinking	Laminate 3: mono-material with <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PE virgin • PE PCR from F origin • Functional barriers and tracers 	FP2: Coffee
Loop 3 cycle 2	Household plastic packaging waste	Mixed – EoL F (mono-material with PCR) and NF flexibles, with tracers in the F flexibles	Delamination and Deinking	Laminate 4: mono-material with <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PE virgin • PE PCR from F origin • Functional barriers and tracers 	FP2: Coffee

As mentioned above, the Loops represent specific cascade cases and are then combined into scenarios in line with the FU of the LCSA model. In the following, a differentiation is established between innovative scenarios for household packaging/plastic waste and business packaging/plastic waste, along with their respective baseline scenarios. The distinction between the system perspective and the material perspective is evident in the area of application and consequently in the outcome. In the former, the focus is on packaging, while in the latter, it shifts to the pellet. From the system perspective, Table 2 visualizes the consideration of two different purification pathways (option A CreaSolv[®] and option B Delamination + Deinking) for the final assessment of three main innovative scenarios and one innovative sub-scenario complemented by two baseline scenarios. For household plastic packaging waste these encompass: (S1) NF packaging from household waste (Loop 1), (S2) F and NF packaging from household waste – (Loop 3 cycle 1 and Loop 1), sub-scenario (S2.1) F and NF packaging from household waste – (Loop 3 cycle 2 and Loop 1) and (S3) Baseline for household waste. For business plastic packaging waste, the scenarios consist of: (S4) F packaging from business waste (Loop 2), and (S5) Baseline for business waste. The decision to evaluate only the two respective demonstrators, i.e. detergent tabs pouches for the NF scenario and coffee pouches for the F scenarios, is driven by their distinct laminate structures, specifically duplex and triplex, respectively. The key insights can be derived from these two laminate structures, and thus these two demonstrators. Additionally, maintaining consistency with the demonstrator for Loop 3 cycle 1 and cycle 2 enables comparison between them. Considering the material perspective, three primary scenarios are examined for household plastic packaging waste input: (M1) the NF pellet scenario - Loop 1, (M2) the F pellet scenario - Loop 3, and (M3) the Baseline pellet scenario. These scenarios result in the production of either recycled PE (rPE) pellets or, in the case of the Baseline scenario, virgin PE (vPE) pellets. The difference between the system and the material perspective is described in more detail in the following subsection.

Table 2: Innovative and baseline scenarios for both the system and the material perspectives. For the innovative scenarios including their purification pathways and demonstrators assessed in this study, NA: non-applicable

Perspective	Input Origin	Scenarios	Purification pathways	Demonstrators/ Product under study
System	Household plastic packaging waste	(S1) NF packaging from household waste (Loop 1)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CreaSolv[®] (for NF) 	HP2: detergent tabs pouch; duplex structure
		(S2) F and NF packaging from household waste – (Loop 3 cycle 1 and Loop 1)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Delamination and Deinking (for F) CreaSolv[®] (for NF) 	FP2: coffee pouch; triplex structure
		(S2.1) F and NF packaging from household waste – (Loop 3 cycle 2 and Loop 1)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Delamination and Deinking (for F packaging) CreaSolv[®] (for NF) 	FP2: coffee pouch; triplex-structure

		(S3) Baseline for household waste	NA	NA
	Business plastic packaging waste	(S4) F packaging from business waste (Loop 2)	• Delamination and Deinking (for F)	FP2: coffee pouch; triplex-structure
		(S5) Baseline for business waste	NA	NA
Material	Household plastic packaging waste	(M1) NF pellet - Loop 1	• CreaSolv® (for NF)	rPE pellet NF grade
		(M2) F pellet - Loop 3	• Delamination and Deinking (for F)	rPE pellet F grade
		(M3) Baseline pellet	NA	vPE pellet

2.1.1. Innovative scenarios and baseline scenario for household plastic packaging waste

Two research questions (RQs) for the innovative scenario and the baseline scenario for household plastic packaging waste are defined:

- RQ 1. From a **sustainability point of view**, what is the best **EOL strategy** for PE-rich mixed food (F) and non-food (NF) flexible waste, resulting in a specific basket of products, including F flexible packaging, NF flexible packaging and energy?
- RQ 2. From a **sustainability point of view**, how does the **performance of rPE compare to vPE** for a specific (F or NF) flexible packaging application?

The incorporation of an additional material perspective (RQ 2), alongside the initial system perspective (RQ 1), as mentioned in deliverable D7.1, has been initiated as a result of discussions within the project consortium and agreed upon during a dedicated meeting in M33. The added value of RQ 2 is the sole focus on the performance of the recycling cascades, excluding the input of virgin material to produce the final packaging. RQ 1 is useful to be considered in addition to RQ 2 because it takes into account the design of the packaging, especially the PCR share.

System perspective (RQ 1)

Figure 2 provides an overview of the three scenarios within the system perspective for household plastic packaging waste, with two innovative scenarios labelled the **(S1) NF packaging** from household waste (**Loop 1**) scenario and the **(S2) F-NF packaging** from household waste (**Loop 3 and 1**) scenario, and the **(S3) Baseline** scenario for household waste. These names were chosen to reflect the input, i.e. the household waste, and the outcome, i.e. food or non-food packaging, of each innovative scenario, alongside the project's experimental loops. For the baseline scenario, the main focus is on investigating the current European waste management of multilayer flexible materials, which traditionally consist of several materials (Ragaert et al., 2017). The baseline scenario was thus

redefined in comparison to Deliverable 7.1, where the waste management of mono-materials through recycling (Eunomia & Plastic Recyclers Europe, 2020) was included.

(S1) NF packaging from household waste (Loop 1)

In the innovative NF scenario, one ton of household PE-rich flexible packaging waste undergoes solvent-based recycling using the CreaSolv[®] purification method, resulting in a non-food packaging laminate with 52% PE PCR in a multilayer mono-material (duplex) structure for detergent tab pouches. Additionally, the incineration of residues with energy recovery generates electricity and heat as outputs.

(S2) F and NF packaging from household waste – (Loop 3 cycle 1 and Loop 1)

In the innovative F-NF scenario **cycle 1**, one ton of household PE-rich flexible packaging waste, including tracers in F flexibles, is sorted by tracer-based sorting, in a F and NF flexible fraction. The mono-material F fraction goes through advanced mechanical recycling with delamination and deinking as the purification method (Loop 3) and the NF fraction goes through the solvent-based recycling (CreaSolv[®]) processes (Loop 1). The outputs include F packaging (triplex) laminate with 50% PE PCR for coffee pouches and NF packaging (duplex) laminate with 52% PE PCR for detergent tab pouches, respectively, along with the generation of electricity and heat from the incineration of residues with energy recovery.

(S2.1) F and NF packaging from household waste – (Loop 3 cycle 2 and Loop 1)

In the innovative F-NF scenario **cycle 2**, one ton of household PE-rich flexible packaging waste, including mono-material flexible F packaging with tracers **and PCR (cycle 1) content**, is sorted by tracer-based sorting, in a F and NF flexible fraction. The F fraction goes through advanced mechanical recycling with delamination and deinking as the purification method (Loop 3) and the NF fraction goes through the solvent-based recycling (CreaSolv^{®6}) processes (Loop 1). The outputs include F packaging (triplex) laminate with up to 50%⁷ PE PCR for coffee pouches and NF packaging (duplex) laminate with 52% PE PCR for detergent tab pouches, respectively, along with the generation of electricity and heat from the incineration of residues with energy recovery.

(S3) Baseline for household waste ⁸

In the Household Baseline scenario, one ton of household PE-rich flexible packaging waste is collected in two ways: 25% is collected through the selective collection, while 75% is collected through mixed collection as municipal waste (Eunomia & Plastic Recyclers Europe, 2020). A portion of flexible films (12%) is lost between collection and sorting (Eunomia & Plastic Recyclers Europe, 2020), with 11% of this fraction sent to incineration with energy recovery and 1% sent to landfilling

⁶ CreaSolv[®] was chosen for Loop 1 due to its ability to handle heterogeneous waste (including various residual fractions) by selective dissolution.

⁷ This is yet to be clarified as progress is made through the project—sensitivity for both optimistic and less optimistic scenarios will be explored.

⁸ The information on the absence of recycling is obtained from Eunomia & Plastic Recyclers Europe, (2020) and relates specifically to PE multi-layer, multi-material from household packaging. This report indicates no current material usage but primary utilization for energy recovery or fuel. The ratio between the collected through selective collection and mixed collection as municipal waste is determined based on the overall flexible films mass balance of 2018 (Eunomia & Plastic Recyclers Europe, 2020). The data for energy recovery and landfilling from Plastic Europe, (2022) pertains to post-consumer plastics packaging for both selective collection and mixed collection in 2020.

(Plastic Europe, 2022). Additionally, 13% of the waste is sent to sorting after selective collection, where pouches are sorted out as residual waste due to their multi-material, multi-layer (MuMu) structure (Eunomia & Plastic Recyclers Europe, 2020), of which 12% are incinerated with energy recovery and 1% is sent to landfill (Plastic Europe, 2022). Regarding the 75% mixed collection of municipal waste, a fraction of 47% is incinerated with energy recovery and 28% is sent to landfill (Plastic Europe, 2022). This is depicted in detail in the baseline process flow scheme in subsection 2.2.2.

Overall, a fraction of 70% is directed to incineration with energy recovery, while the remaining fraction of 30% is sent to landfills (Eunomia & Plastic Recyclers Europe, 2020; Plastic Europe, 2022). The resulting outputs comprise the generation of electricity and heat from incineration.

Figure 2: Overview of main innovative and baseline scenarios for household waste within the system perspective, S3

The comparison of three main scenarios (S1-3) through the basket of products approach was selected for the system perspective (RQ 1). The scope extends from waste collection to packaging production. Thus, the functional unit (FU) can be defined as the treatment and recovery of one ton of sorted PE-rich household flexible packaging waste leading to a specific basket of products. A basket of products refers to a collection of product groups (European Commission, 2012). In this household waste scenario (1) F packaging, (2) NF packaging, and (3) energy (electricity and heat) recovered from incineration, are considered as the basket of products. To address the basket of products, a system expansion approach is applied, which results in a system that produces the function(s) expressed by the functional unit, as well as the additional function(s) in the basket (Heijungs et al., 2021). For these additional functions in the system expansion, the substituted product systems are considered. Substituted product systems do not rely on the FU (i.e. sorted PE-rich household flexible packaging waste). As an illustration, the output of the Baseline scenario includes energy. Therefore, the system expansion for the Baseline scenario encompasses both F packaging and NF packaging. The packaging in the system expansion of the Baseline scenario is made of 100% virgin materials (i.e. 0% PCR).

Figure 3: Visualisation of the basket of products approach used in case of the system perspective for household waste, Scenarios S1, S2, S3

Material perspective (RQ2)

To address RQ2 a comparison of three main scenarios (M1-3) was selected using the material perspective approach. The scope extends from waste collection to pellet production. Consequently, the functional unit (FU) is defined as the production of one ton of material, specifically PE pellets, with a defined quality for flexible packaging applications. The considered products vary between rPE with food-grade specifications, rPE without food-grade specifications, and vPE. Besides food-grade specifications, each F or NF product type demands specific material requirements (e.g., mechanical properties, processability properties, colour, etc.). Depending on the specific F or NF application, different PE grades can therefore be preferred, which are not considered in such detail in this study. In order to account for substitution by crediting avoided burdens the circular foot print formula (Pant et al., 2019) will be applied.

(M1) NF pellet scenario - Loop 1

In the innovative NF pellet scenario, household PE-rich flexible packaging waste undergoes solvent-based recycling using the CreaSolv® purification method, resulting in the production of one ton of non-food grade rPE pellet for flexible packaging applications.

(M2) F pellet scenario - Loop 3

In the innovative F pellet scenario, household PE-rich flexible packaging waste undergoes tracer-based sorting to separate F flexibles from NF flexibles. The F fraction then undergoes advanced mechanical recycling with delamination and deinking as the purification method, resulting in the production of one ton of food-grade rPE pellets for flexible packaging applications.

(M3) Baseline pellet scenario

In the scenario of Baseline pellets, virgin (fossil-based) raw materials are used to produce one ton vPE pellets, which are suitable for both NF and F flexible packaging applications.

Figure 4: Visualisation of the approach used in case of the material perspective for household waste, Scenarios M1, M2, M3, rPE: recycled PE, vPE: virgin PE

2.1.2. Innovative scenario and baseline scenario for business plastic packaging waste

For the innovative scenario and the baseline scenario for business plastic packaging waste, one research question (RQ 3) was defined.

- RQ 3. From a **sustainability point of view**, what is the best **EOL strategy** for PE-rich **F business flexible waste**, resulting in a specific basket of products, including F flexible packaging and energy?

This research question follows thus a system perspective (i.e. RQ 1 for household waste).

Figure 5 provides an overview of the two scenarios relating to the business waste, with one innovative scenario labelled the **(S4) F packaging from business waste (Loop 2)** and one **(S5) Baseline** for business waste.

(S4) F packaging from business waste (Loop 2)

In this innovative scenario, one ton of business PE-rich flexible packaging waste (from coffee pouches), is collected through a reverse-logistics scheme and goes through advanced mechanical recycling with delamination and deinking as the purification method. The resulting outputs consist of F packaging (triplex) laminate with 50% PE PCR for coffee pouches, complemented by the recovery of electricity and heat through the incineration of residues.

(S5) Baseline for business waste

In this scenario, one ton of business PE-rich flexible packaging waste (from coffee pouches), is collected, of which 25% through the selective collection and 75% through the mixed collection as municipal waste (Eunomia & Plastic Recyclers Europe, 2020). Overall, for the total amount of waste, a fraction of 70% is directed to incineration with energy recovery (electricity and heat), while the

remaining fraction of 30% is sent to landfills (Eunomia & Plastic Recyclers Europe, 2020; Plastic Europe, 2022). More details are provided in subsection 2.2.2. Baseline scenarios.

Figure 5 Overview of EOL scenarios for PE-rich business flexible packaging waste, S4, S5

The comparison of two scenarios (Business, F packaging - Loop 2 and Business waste, Baseline) through the basket of products approach was selected for the system perspective (RQ 3). Thus, the functional unit (FU) can be defined as the treatment and recovery of one ton of PE-rich business flexible packaging leading to the creation of a specific basket of products. In this business waste scenario (1) F packaging and (2) energy (electricity and heat) recovered from incineration, are considered as the basket of products. To address the basket of products, a system expansion approach is applied. This involves integrating the product system being replaced (such as virgin laminate) into the product system under study (Heijungs et al., 2021). For instance, in the Baseline scenario where the output product is energy, the system expansion includes F packaging. The additional laminates resulting from the system expansion consist entirely of virgin materials (i.e., 0% PCR).

Figure 6: Visualisation of the basket of product approach used for the system perspective for business waste, Scenarios S4, S5

2.2. Process flow schemes

Table 3 shows the partners and one company external to the CFP project consortium involved in relation to the developed process flow schemes within this project.

Table 3: Involved partners per process step

Partners	Process
SUEZ	Collection, SoA sorting and Pretreatment
POLY	Tracer-based sorting and tracer production
UGENT ⁹	Purification (Delamination and Deinking)
IVV	Purification (CreaSolv [®])
SUEZ	Recompounding
KREYEN	Deodorization
AMCOR	Laminate production (including film production and printing)
SIEGWERK	Ink, heat protective lacquer and primer production
NESTLE	B2B collection, F packaging production
MESPACK ¹⁰	NF packaging production

⁹ NTCP and HYDRODYN are subcontractors for the pilot scale trials of delamination and deinking.

¹⁰ MESPACK collaborates with AMCOR as a machine supplier for non-food packaging, with AMCOR serving as the primary contact point with the external company.

In order to draw the process flow schemes, bilateral meetings were held focusing on the inputs and outputs of each process step. System boundaries and process flow schemes were drawn for the following processes:

- Collection
- SoA sorting
- Tracer-based sorting
- Pretreatment
 - Oversorting
 - Shredding
 - Washing
 - Grinding
 - Float-sink separation
- Purification option A-CreaSolv®
- Purification option B-Deinking and Delamination
- Posttreatment Recompounding
- Posttreatment Deodorization
- Laminate production (including film production and printing)
- Ink production
- Primer production
- Heat-protective lacquer production
- Tracer production
- F and NF packaging production.

The system boundaries are divided into foreground and background systems. The former consists of the core processes in the product's life cycle for which direct access to information is available (i.e. the ones conducted by the Consortium partners/subcontractors in the project) while the latter includes other processes in the product's life cycle for which no direct access to information is possible (e.g. production of virgin pellets, chemicals, electricity, etc.) (European Commission, 2013).

The overall process flow schemes per innovative scenario (Figure 7-Figure 14) and per baseline scenario (Figure 15-Figure 16) are described first, followed by the detailed process flow schemes of each process step i.e. collection, sorting and pretreatment (Figure 18-Figure 20), purification (Figure 21-Figure 23), posttreatment (Figure 24 and Figure 25), laminate production (Figure 27-Figure 29), tracer-, ink- heat-protective lacquer and primer production (Figure 34-Figure 37) and F and NF packaging production (Figure 39).

2.2.1. Innovative scenarios

Figure 7-Figure 10 illustrate the process flow schemes for the scenarios from the system perspective i.e., for (S1) NF packaging from household waste (Loop 1), (S2) F and NF packaging from household waste – (Loop 3 cycle 1-2 and Loop 1) and (S4) F packaging from business waste (Loop 2), whereas Figure 13-Figure 14 depict the process flow schemes for the scenarios from the material perspective i.e. (M1) NF pellet - Loop 1 and (M2) F pellet - Loop 3.

The scenarios differ in terms of their inputs as depicted in the process flow charts. While the input for the (S1) NF packaging from household waste (Loop 1) scenario (Figure 7-Figure 8) and the (S2) F

and NF packaging from household waste – (Loop 3 cycle 1-2 and Loop 1) (Figure 9-Figure 10) originates from packaging/plastic household waste, the input for the (S4) F packaging from business waste (Loop 2) comes from business consumers (Figure 11-Figure 12). In the (S2) F and NF packaging from household waste – (Loop 3 cycle 1-2 and Loop 1), tracer-based sorting (TBS) technology has been introduced alongside state-of-the-art (SoA) near-infrared (NIR) sorting to ensure that the developed food packaging with tracers (depicted in Figure 10) is separated from the waste stream. Furthermore, there is a difference in the output of the scenarios: the (S1) NF packaging from household waste (Loop 1) scenario produces laminate for NF applications, the (S4) F packaging from business waste (Loop 2) produces laminates for F applications, and the (S2) F and NF packaging from household waste – (Loop 3 cycle 1-2 and Loop 1) produces both.

(S1) NF packaging from household waste (Loop 1)

Figure 7 depicts an overview of processes involved in the (S1) NF packaging from household waste (Loop 1) for the system perspective. The colours of the boxes represent the main process categories and remain consistent throughout the document for easy tracking. Operations involving residues considered for this assessment are in line with the FU which includes one ton of PE-rich sorted household flexibles. Therefore, although other waste fractions (e.g. paper, aluminium) are outputs of the sorting step, they are treated by other recycling processes, which are not considered in the system boundary.

Figure 7: Overview of the (S1) NF packaging from household waste (Loop 1) process flow scheme for the system perspective

Figure 8 shows the foreground system boundary and involved processes of (S1) NF packaging from household waste (Loop 1) for the system perspective where the selective dissolution (CreaSolv[®]) purification method is employed. Different types of mass flows containing household waste and its derivatives are shown. The colours of the boxes represent the main process categories shown in Figure 7. The ancillary material and energy flows for each process unit are further represented in subsection 2.2.3-2.2.6. The listing of filling and the flow of unpacked products is purely for illustrative purposes and is not considered in the assessments. The initial short-term storage post-packing falls within the system boundaries.

Figure 8: Foreground system boundary and involved processes of (S1) NF packaging from household waste (Loop 1) for the system perspective; OPV: heat protective lacquer

(S2) F and NF packaging from household waste – (Loop 3 cycle 1-2 and Loop 1)

Figure 9 depicts an overview of processes involved in the *(S2) F and NF packaging from household waste – (Loop 3 cycle 1-2 and Loop 1)* for the system perspective.

Figure 9: Overview of the *(S2) F and NF packaging from household waste – (Loop 3 cycle 1-2 and Loop 1)* process flow scheme for the system perspective, The processes highlighted with a grey box pertain specifically to Loop 1, while those highlighted with a light green box in the foreground system are specific to Loop 3.

TB sorting separates the flexibles into both a food source, which is treated with delamination and deinking purification method, highlighted in light green, and a non-food source, which is sent to the *NF packaging from household waste (Loop 1)* process, highlighted in grey. Different types of mass flows containing household waste and its derivatives are shown. The colours of the boxes represent the main process categories shown in Figure 9. The two different shades of blue in the post-treatment box represent the successive processes of recompounding and deodorization. The processes highlighted with a grey box in the legend pertain specifically to Loop 1, while those highlighted with a light green box in the foreground system are specific to Loop 3 (Figure 11). The ancillary material and energy flows for each process unit are further represented in subsection 2.2.3-2.2.6.

Figure 10: Foreground system boundary and involved processes of (S2) F and NF packaging from household waste – (Loop 3 cycle 1-2 and Loop 1) for the system perspective; OPV: heat protective lacquer

(S4) F packaging from business waste (Loop 2)

Figure 11 depicts an overview of processes involved in (S4) F packaging from business waste (Loop 2) for the system perspective.

Figure 11: Overview of the (S4) F packaging from business waste (Loop 2) flow scheme for the system perspective

In the (S4) F packaging from business waste (Loop 2) the delamination and deinking purification method is employed. Different types of mass flows containing business waste and its derivatives are shown. The colours of the boxes represent the main process categories shown in Figure 11. The two different shades of blue in the post-treatment box represent the successive processes of recompounding and deodorization. The ancillary material and energy flows for each process unit are further represented in subsection 2.2.3-2.2.6.

Figure 12: Foreground system boundary and involved processes of Business, F packaging scenario - Loop 2 for the system perspective; OPV: heat protective lacquer

(M1) NF pellet scenario - Loop 1

Figure 13 shows the (M1) NF pellet scenario - Loop 1 process flow scheme for the material perspective.

Figure 13: (M1) NF pellet scenario - Loop 1 process flow scheme for the material perspective

(M2) F pellet scenario - Loop 3

Figure 14 represents the (M2) F pellet scenario - Loop 3 process flow scheme for the material perspective.

Figure 14: (M2) F pellet scenario - Loop 3 process flow scheme for the material perspective

2.2.2. Baseline scenarios

The presence of selective collection systems for plastic packaging varies among EU countries. While many EU nations have adopted selective collection systems for plastic packaging, the precise count may fluctuate over time due to shifts in policy and waste management practices. In 2020, combined mixed waste collection and selective post-consumer plastics packaging waste collection totaled 17.9 million tons (Mt) in the EU27+3, with 44% attributed to mixed waste collection and 56% to selective collection (Plastic Europe, 2022). However, for multilayer packaging, the selective collection¹¹ rate is notably lower, standing at only 25% of the 2,240 kt multilayers placed on the market in 2018 (Eunomia & Plastic Recyclers Europe, 2020). Consequently, this study employs a 75:25 split between mixed waste collection of multilayer plastic packaging as municipal waste and selective collection systems to reflect the European perspective. As the Eunomia & Plastic Recyclers Europe, (2020) report lacks specific data regarding the amount of waste directed to incineration with energy recovery and landfill, the figures are extrapolated from Plastic Europe, (2022), considering only the distribution between landfill and energy recovery.

In upcoming studies, these distributions can be adjusted or updated as necessary. According to the EU Waste Framework Directive, EU member states are obliged to increase the proportion of municipal waste processed for reuse or recycling to 55% by 2025, 60% by 2030 and 65% by 2035. In addition, the EU Landfill Directive stipulates that no more than 10% of all municipal waste should be landfilled by 2035 (European Environment Agency, 2023).

The process flow scheme for the Baseline Scenario for household waste - Loop 1 and 3 is presented in Figure 21 15, while the process flow scheme for the Baseline Scenario for business waste - Loop 2 is visualised in Figure 16. The current waste treatment of multi-material multi-layers combines incineration with energy recovery and landfilling (Eunomia & Plastic Recyclers Europe, 2020; Plastic Europe, 2022). As the waste input, i.e. non-food and food flexibles (Loop 1), solely food flexibles (Loop 2), or non-food flexibles and food flexibles with tracers (Loop 3), differs depending on the respective Loop, the baseline scenarios are adapted accordingly.

¹¹ Selective collection includes multilayer packaging as part of plastic packaging waste.

The integration of virgin packaging production resulting from system expansion is included in the process flow schemes of the baseline scenarios for the system perspective, aligning with the functional unit of the basket of products and driven by the inherent causal relationship i.e., the demand for virgin material resulting from the incineration and landfilling of plastic packaging waste feedstock.

Figure 17 visualizes the Baseline pellet scenario process flow scheme for the virgin PE pellet production from the material perspective.

(S3) Baseline scenario for household waste

Figure 15 represents the baseline scenario process flow scheme for the household waste scenarios from the system perspective. In the Household Baseline scenario, household PE-rich flexible packaging waste, undergoes collection through two methods: 25% via selective collection and 75% through mixed collection as municipal waste (Eunomia & Plastic Recyclers Europe, 2020). Approximately 12% of flexible films are lost between collection and sorting, with 11% of this fraction incinerated with energy recovery and 1% sent to landfilling (Plastic Europe, 2022). After selective collection, 13% of the waste undergoes sorting, where pouches are separated due to their multi-material, multi-layer (MuMu) structure (Eunomia & Plastic Recyclers Europe, 2020). Of this, 12% are incinerated with energy recovery and 1% are sent to landfills (Plastic Europe, 2022). Of the 75% mixed collection, 47% is incinerated with energy recovery and 28% is sent to landfill (Plastic Europe, 2022). Overall, a fraction of 70% is directed to incineration with energy recovery, while the remaining fraction of 30% is sent to landfills (Eunomia & Plastic Recyclers Europe, 2020; Plastic Europe, 2022). The resulting outputs comprise the generation of electricity and heat. The virgin packaging production resulting from system expansion is included in the system boundary. One laminate structure suitable for both for NF (Loop1) and F (Loop3) applications is presented in alignment with the basket of products. In general, the product filling process occurs outside the system boundary.

Figure 15: Baseline scenario (S3) process flow scheme for the household waste scenarios of system perspective

(S5) Baseline scenario for business waste

Figure 16 depicts the process flow scheme for the baseline business waste scenario. In the baseline business waste scenario, business PE-rich flexible packaging waste (coffee pouches), follows the same collection and treatment route as described in scenario (S3) for household waste. This is assumption is based on SUEZ's experience that in densely populated areas and for small restaurants and cafés, the same collection system is used as for household waste. The virgin F packaging production resulting from system expansion is included in the system boundary.

Figure 16: Baseline scenario (S5) process flow scheme for the business waste scenario

Baseline for pellet scenario - Loop 1 and 3

Figure 17 describes the process flow scheme for the baseline pellet scenario from the material perspective, where vPE pellets, suitable for both non-food and food applications, are produced using virgin fossil-based raw materials. Secondary data from a respective *ecoinvent* dataset will be used, hence the processes are presented as a closed system or a “black box” (Rebe Feraldi & Cashman, 2011).

Figure 17: Baseline pellet scenario process flow scheme for the virgin PE pellet production of the material perspective

In what follows, the process steps are presented in terms of chronological sequence and in relation to their use in the respective use cases (Loops 1-3).

2.2.3. Collection, Sorting and Pretreatment

The process flow scheme for Collection and SoA sorting and Pretreatment within Loop 1 is shown in Figure 18 based on information provided by SUEZ. The residues from SoA sorting, Oversorting, Wastewater treatment and Float-sink separation are sent to incineration with energy recovery.

Figure 18: Loop 1 Collection and SoA sorting and Pretreatment process flow scheme

The process flow scheme for Collection and SoA sorting and Pretreatment within Loop 2 is shown in Figure 19 based on information provided by SUEZ and NESTLE. The SoA sorting step is omitted because the input material is collected from companies (B2B) by NESTLE in a reverse logistic approach, resulting in a homogeneous stream that does not require SoA sorting apart from Oversorting.

Loop 2

Figure 19: Loop 2 Collection and Pretreatment process flow scheme

The process flow scheme for Collection and SoA sorting and Pretreatment within Loop 3 is shown in Figure 20 based on information provided by SUEZ and POLY. An additional TB sorting step is applied here.

Loop 3 including Tracer-based sorting (POLY)

Figure 20: Loop 3 Collection and SoA sorting and Pretreatment process flow scheme

2.2.4. Purification option A CreaSolv®

The process flow scheme for Purification option A CreaSolv® within Loop 1 is presented in Figure 21 based on information provided by IVV. No additive is added to the system for this study.

Loop 1

Figure 21: Loops 1 Purification option A CreaSolv® process flow scheme

2.2.5. Purification option B Delamination and Deinking

The process flow scheme for Purification option B Delamination and Deinking within Loop 2 is shown in Figure 22 based on information provided by UGENT and HYDRODYN.

Loop 2

Figure 22: Loop 2 Purification option B Delamination and Deinking process flow scheme

The process flow scheme for Purification option B Delamination and Deinking within Loop 3 is shown in Figure 23 based on information provided by UGENT and NTCP.

Loop 3

Figure 23: Loop 3 Purification option B Delamination and Deinking process flow scheme

2.2.1. Post-treatment Recompounding

The process flow scheme for Recompounding within Loop 2-3 is shown in Figure 24 based on information provided by SUEZ. For Loop 1 Recompounding (i.e., pelletizing) is included in the Creasolv® process. A final decision must be made if additives are added in the regranulation step. The input (PE PCR flakes) comes from the Purification option B (Delamination and deinking) and the output (PE PCR pellets) goes to Deodorization.

Loop 2 and 3

Figure 24: Loop 2 and 3 Recompounding process flow scheme

2.2.2. Post-treatment Deodorization

The process flow scheme for Deodorization within Loop 1 is presented in Figure 25 and for Loop 2 and 3 in Figure 26 based on information provided by KREYEN. It consists of infrared and thermal treatment with air, electricity, and heat supplied to the system, and VOCs are emitted to the atmosphere. Depending on the outcome of the different purification pathways the input (PE PCR pellets) comes either from the Purification option A Creasolv[®] (Loop 1) or Recompounding (Loop 2 and 3).

Loop 1

Figure 25 Loop 1 Deodorization process flow scheme

Loop 2 and 3

Figure 26: Loop 2 and 3 Deodorization process flow scheme

2.2.3. Laminate production

The process flow scheme for Laminate production within the Loop 1 NF scenario, Loop 2 F scenario and Loop 3 F scenario is presented in Figure 27-Figure 29 based on information provided by AMCOR and is shown for two applications, i.e. detergent tabs (HP2) and coffee (FP2). Laminate production involves, in the first step, the production of films, which are then processed into a printed laminate. The Loop 1 NF scenario- Detergent tabs (HP2) includes PCR in the MDOPE25 film. MDOPE25 film is subjected to a special process where the film is stretched in the machine's running direction. MDO stands for machine-direction orientation.

Loop 1 NF scenario- Detergent tabs (HP2)

Figure 27: Loop 1 NF scenario- Detergent tabs (HP2) laminate production process flow scheme

Loop 2 F scenario- Coffee (FP2)

Figure 28: Loop 2 F scenario- Coffee (FP2) laminate production process flow scheme

Loop 3 F scenario- Coffee (FP2)

Figure 29: Loop 3 F scenario- Coffee (FP2) laminate production process flow scheme

The alternative, virgin laminates for food and non-food packaging for Loops 1-3 are likewise manufactured by AMCOR. Here, a differentiation can be made between a multi-material multilayer structure (MuMu) (Figure 30-Figure 31) and a mono-material multilayer structure (MoMu) (Figure 32-Figure 33). For the Baseline assessment, the inclusion of the MuMu structure for NF and F application (Figure 30) is considered as system expansion due to its alignment with the functional unit and the project's emphasis on the waste management of this structure. The difference between the MuMu laminate for NF applications (duplex) and the MuMu laminate for NF and F applications (triplex) lies primarily in the inclusion of aluminum foil in the latter to ensure the oxygen barrier. The MuMu laminate for NF applications (duplex) will be added to the system expansion in a scenario analysis. Additionally, the inclusion of the MoMu structure allows for an additional scenario analysis and facilitates understanding of the impact of transitioning from a multi-material to a mono-material laminate structure. Figure 32 illustrates the Loop 1 Baseline scenario, depicting the production process flow for MoMu laminate. In this context, the applications can be in general either NF or possibly F, excluding high-barrier F applications like coffee powder, which are designated for Loop 3. EVOH in all structures stands for ethylene vinyl alcohol copolymer, which is added as functional barrier.

Loops 1-3 Baseline scenario- MuMu laminate for NF and F applications

Figure 30: Loop 1-3 Baseline scenario- MuMu laminate (NF and F) production process flow scheme

Loop 1 Baseline scenario- MuMu laminate for NF applications for scenario analysis

Figure 31: Loop 1 Baseline scenario- MuMu laminate (NF) production process flow scheme

Loop 1 Baseline scenario- MoMu laminate for NF applications for scenario analysis

Figure 32 Loop 1 Baseline scenario- MoMu laminate (NF) production process flow scheme.

Loop 3 Baseline scenario- MoMu laminate for F applications for scenario analysis

Figure 33: Loop 3 Baseline scenario- MoMu laminate (F) production process flow scheme

2.2.4. Tracer production

The process flow scheme for Tracer production within Loop 3 is presented in Figure 34 based on information provided by POLY. Tracers will be implemented in the laminate production of Loop 3.

Loop 3

Figure 34: Loop 3 Tracer production process flow scheme

2.2.5. Ink, Primer and Heat protective lacquer production

The process flow scheme for Ink, Primer and Heat protective lacquer production is based on information provided by Siegart. Ink production within Loops 1-3 is detailed in Figure 35-Figure 36, while Primer production within Loops 2-3 is outlined in Figure 37. Primers will be integrated into laminate production in Loops 2-3 to aid the purification process of delamination and deinking. Heat protective lacquer production, essential for ensuring optimal processability during the sealing process for packaging, is illustrated in Figure 38.

Loops 1-2 Ink

Figure 35: Loops 1-2 Ink production process flow scheme

Due to the input of tracers the production of inks for Loop 3 is different to Loop 1-2.

Loop 3 Ink

Figure 36: Loop 3 Ink production process flow scheme

Loops 2-3 Primer

Figure 37: Loops 2-3 Primer production process flow scheme

Loops 1-3 Heat protective lacquer

Figure 38: Loops 1-3 Heat protective lacquer production process flow scheme

2.2.6. Food and non-food packaging production

The process flow scheme for the F and NF packaging production within Loops 1 - 3 is presented in Figure 39 based on information provided by MESPAC and NESTLE.

Loops 1-3

Figure 39: Loops 1-3 Food and non-food packaging production process flow scheme

3. DATA INVENTORIES

The life cycle inventory analysis phase (LCI phase) is the second stage of the life cycle assessment. It comprises the compilation of the input/output data of the system to be analysed and includes the collection of the data required to fulfil the study objectives (ISO 14044, 2006). To derive mass and energy balances for the LCA, collect cost data for the LCC assessment and collect data for the S-LCA, the partners were provided with templates for data collection. These filled templates served as the basis for generating the preliminary LCA and LCC results. Throughout the project, certain data points were added, refined, and updated. A particular focus was placed on the Business, F packaging scenario (Loop 2), including Business to Business (B2B) collection, Pretreatment, and the Baseline scenario. Additionally, attention was given to Delamination and Deinking, Laminate Production, and Food and non-food packaging production, addressing data gaps and updates resulting from process improvements. In addition, a great effort was made to collect the data for S-LCA from all project partners.

3.1. Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) data collection

Table 4 illustrates a data collection template for LCA. Data is preferably collected for each process step to facilitate the identification of hotspots within the system. Furthermore, data is collected per specified reference flow e.g., per year, per tonne of waste processed, or per m² of laminate produced, depending on the process. The reference flow represents the measure of output necessary to fulfil the function defined by the functional unit (ISO 14044, 2006). Each unit, such as kWh for electricity or kg for input materials, is inserted. Additional relevant information for the analysis is included in the origin, destination or remark section, with corresponding sources indicated accordingly.

Table 4: Example of Data collection template for Life Cycle Assessment (LCA)

Process 1						
Inputs	Data/year	Data/ton	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
Input 1						
Input 2						
...						
example:						
Electricity	10 000		MWh	Grid Belgium		Excel "...xls" or e-mail company x on 02/02
Outputs	Data per year	Data per ton	Unit	Destination	Remarks	Source
Output 1						
...						
Process 2						
Inputs	Data/year	Data/ton	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
Input 1						
Input 2						
...						
Outputs	Data/year	Data/ton	Unit	Destination	Remarks	Source
Output 2						
...						
Transport (T)						
T1	Distance	Transport mode	Unit	Truck technology	Remarks	Source
Input 1		Lorry	km	EURO 6	please specify truck payload e.g. 3,5t-7,5t; 7,5t-16t, 16t-32t, >32t	
T2	Distance	Transport mode	Unit	Truck technology	Remarks	Source
Input 2		Lorry	km	EURO 6	please specify truck payload e.g. 3,5t-7,5t; 7,5t-16t, 16t-32t, >32t	

3.2. Life Cycle Costing (LCC) data collection

Life cycle costing (LCC) involves an economic assessment that considers various stages of the life cycle. This is an approach that generally covers the costs directly generated by a specific actor (Hunkeler et al., 2008). Costs are categorized into capital expenditure (CAPEX), operating expenditure (OPEX), and revenues, and grouped by cost type (Taelman et al., 2020). For instance, this may include expenses related to equipment investment, personnel, materials, utilities, transportation, emissions, waste, or other operational costs such as taxes and insurance.

Table 5: Data collection template for Life Cycle Costing (LCC)

CAPEX, OPEX, Revenues					
Type of cost	Cost points	Quantity	Unit	Remarks	Source
<i>Capital costs</i>					
Investment	Land		€/m ²		
	Buildings/ property		€/m ²	e.g. industrial plant	
	Equipment/ software		€/pc. or year	e.g. machinery	e.g. Corporate Carbon Footprint (CCF)
	Vehicles		€/pc. or year		e.g. CCF
<i>Operational costs</i>					
Personnel	Salary and wages		€/hour	Please report an average if necessary	
Services	Fee		€/hour		
Material costs	Raw materials		€/kg or m ³	e.g. sand, iron, chemicals	
	Industrial intermediate goods		€/kg or m ³	e.g. steel, plastic, glass, etc.	
Utility costs	Fuel		€/kg; l		
	Freshwater		€/m ³ ;l		
	Electricity		€/kWh		
	Heat		€/MJ		
Transport	Travel and vehicle expenses		€/km	e.g. transport of people and goods	
Emission discharge & waste related costs	Wastewater		€/m ³	e.g. cost of waste management i.e. wastewater fee	
	Emissions		€ per kg of release	e.g. CO ₂ emission tax	
Other operational costs	License, legal, ...		€/year		
	Maintenance and repairs		€/year		
	Taxes		€/year		
	Insurance		€/year		
<i>Revenues/ Positive Cash flows</i>					
Selling of products	Product		€/product	Market prices for secondary products	
	Co-product		€/product	Market prices for secondary products	
	Fees		€/year	e.g. inhabitants that pay a fee to collect their waste	
	Subsidies		€/year	e.g. for setting up a waste recycling management system	

3.3. Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA) data collection

Table 6 presents a section of the data collection template for Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA), designed to facilitate data collection within companies. An information box is provided to aid individuals responsible for gathering S-LCA data who may not be familiar with the specific terms elaborated within the project consortium.

Table 6: Data collection template for Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA) part 1 (infobox)

Indicator	Info box
General Information	<p>Please enter the value for the number of employees in your company in full-time equivalent (FTE).</p> <p>The organization can report the number of employees additionally in head counts.</p> <p>Reporting these numbers in head count gives insight into the number of individual employees, whether full-time or part-time employed.</p> <p>Reporting these numbers in FTE gives insight into the hours worked.</p>
Existence of record of proof of age	<p>Please report the value for the number of records per 1000 employees in the company/y.</p>
Existence of certified environmental management system (EMS)	<p>Please report with yes/no on the following parameters regarding the type of Environmental management system (EMS) in place.</p> <p>ISO 14001:2015 Environmental management systems — Requirements with guidance for use</p> <p>ISO 19011:2011 Guidelines for auditing management systems.</p> <p>Environmental Management Systems: Myth or Magic? – The Auditor (theauditoronline.com)</p>
Percentage of workers who are paid a living wage or above	<p>Your reported number is dependent on a specific country value and year please see info on Categories 2023.</p> <p>If living wage does not apply in the company’s country, (e.g. CH) the number on minimum wage must be indicated.</p> <p>“Living Wage per month is defined as the income needed for a decent living, i. e. the monthly wage needed to cover the necessary living costs of an individual or family.” (WageIndicator, 2019)</p> <p>“A national minimum wage is the lowest gross wage a full-time worker can be remunerated in specific country, defined by national law and legally binding.” (WageIndicator, 2014)</p>
Percentage of (fatal and non-fatal) accidents/injuries in the organization	<p>Please enter the values for the number of non-fatal and fatal accidents per 1000 employees in the company/y</p>
Existence of research and development (R&D)	<p>Please indicate with yes/no if R&D department exists and report the values for gross profit and R&D expenses of the company respectively.</p>
Extent of safety training	<p>Please enter the value of the average hours of training on occupational health and safety per employee in the company/y.</p> <p>When describing the occupational health and safety training provided, the reporting organization can include additional information on:</p>

	<p>In order to establish a reference scale, please also provide the total number of training hours per total number of employees and a breakdown between production and non-production employees</p> <p>In the context of this, 'training' refers to: -all types of vocational training and instruction; -paid educational leave provided by an organization for its employees; -training or education pursued externally and paid for in whole or in part by an organization; -training on specific topics.</p>
Existence of health risk assessments regarding toxicity	Please report with yes/no/not applicable (n.a.) on the following parameters
Percentage of male/female employees	<p>Report a breakdown of the total number of employees, by gender in full-time equivalent (FTE). Gender as specified by the employees themselves.</p> <p>The organization can report a breakdown by gender on the numbers of non-guaranteed hours, full-time, and part-time employees in full-time equivalent (FTE).</p> <p>Non-guaranteed hours employees are employed by the organization without a guarantee of a minimum or fixed number of working hours. The employee may need to make themselves available for work as required, but the organization is not contractually obligated to offer the employee a minimum or fixed number of working hours per day, week, or month. Casual employees, employees with zero-hour contracts, and on-call employees are examples that fall under this category.</p>
Existence of extended producer responsibility (EPR) policy	Please report with yes/no/not applicable (n.a.) on the following parameter.
Existence of formal policy against discrimination	<p>Please report with yes/no on the following parameter and indicate total number of incidents of discrimination during the reporting period.</p> <p>Discrimination: act and result of treating persons unequally by imposing unequal burdens or denying benefits instead of treating each person fairly on the basis of individual merit</p> <p>Disclosure 406-1 discrimination on grounds of race, color, sex, religion, political opinion, national extraction, or social origin as defined by the ILO, or other relevant forms</p>

Additional information regarding the indicator "Percentage of employees earning a living wage or more" includes the living wage categories for Germany, France, Belgium, and Switzerland in 2023 (

Table 7). The data collection template for S-LCA part 2 focusing on the data inventory is presented in the Annex due to the dimension of the table and to ensure a better overview in the document.

Table 7: Living Wage Categories 2023 additional information for the indicator Percentage of workers who are paid a living wage or above for Germany, France, Belgium and Switzerland

Categories 2023	GER	FR	BE	CH
category A Living Wage - Standard family, upper bound is above	€ 2 684	€ 2 220	€ 3 139	-
category B Living Wage - Standard family, lower bound is above	€ 1 932	€ 1 682	€ 2 248	-
category C Living Wage - Single adult, upper bound is above	€ 1 500	€ 1 203	€ 1 835	-
category D Living Wage - Single adult, lower bound is above	€ 1 391	€ 1 112	€ 1 465	-
Minimum wage is above	€ 1 987	€ 1 709	€ 1 955	3 600 CHF

4. CONCLUSION

To conduct a comprehensive life cycle analysis of the technologies and concepts developed within the CIRCULAR FoodPack project, scenarios, process flow schemes, and mass and energy balances were established. The study encompasses Europe geographically and involves data collection from 2021 to 2024. It includes prospective aspects, particularly focusing on technologies that are not fully operational at an industrial level yet, but currently undergoing pilot-scale testing. The scenarios are designed with the goal of eventual industrial implementation including prospective considerations for e.g. business waste collection through reverse logistic, which is not yet operational. The developed scenarios represent either a system or material perspective, as outlined below:

System Perspective:

Household plastic packaging waste:

- Scenario S1: Household NF Packaging - Loop 1
- Scenario S2: Household F and NF Packaging - Loop 3 Cycle 1 and Loop 1
- Scenario S2.1: Household F and NF Packaging - Loop 3 Cycle 2 and Loop 1
- Scenario S3: Baseline for household waste

Business plastic packaging waste:

- Scenario S4: Business F Packaging – Loop 2
- Scenario S5: Business Waste Baseline

Material Perspective:

Household plastic packaging waste:

- Scenario M1: NF Pellet - Loop 1
- Scenario M2: F Pellet - Loop 3
- Scenario M3: Baseline Pellet

The FU chosen for comparison from a system perspective (RQ 1, RQ 3), involves the basket of products approach, encompassing non-food packaging, food packaging, and recovered energy and heat for household waste scenarios, and solely food packaging and recovered energy and heat for the business waste scenario. From a material perspective, the FU is defined as the production of one ton of material, specifically PE pellets, with a defined quality for flexible packaging applications.

The purification pathways in the scenarios being investigated involve using CreaSolv[®] for producing rPE pellet NF grade and NF laminate out of mixed packaging plastic waste, while delamination and deinking are employed for producing rPE pellet F grade and F laminate from flexible mono-material food packaging waste. The selected demonstrators for NF application are detergent tabs pouch (HP2), and for F application, coffee pouch (FP2), chosen based on their different laminate structures—duplex for detergent tabs pouch and triplex for coffee pouch. The key insights can be derived from these two laminate structures, summarized below:

Purification Pathways | Demonstrators/Product Under Study

- CreaSolv[®] (for NF laminate) | HP2: detergent tabs pouch
- Delamination and Deinking (for F laminate) | FP2: coffee pouch
- CreaSolv[®] (for NF pellet) | rPE pellet NF grade
- Delamination and Deinking (for F pellet) | rPE pellet F grade

In the scenario of *Household NF Packaging - Loop 1*, the input originates from household waste, consisting of mixed EoL flexible packaging from both F and NF items, which undergoes the

purification pathway of CreaSolv® producing NF laminate with 52% PCR for detergent pouches. For *Business F Packaging - Loop 2*, the input comes from business waste, specifically EoL F flexibles, which undergo delamination and deinking for purification producing F laminate with 50% PCR for coffee pouches.

In the *Household F and NF Packaging - Cycle 1 - Loop 3 Cycle 1 and Loop 1* scenario, the input from household waste comprises mixed EoL F and NF flexibles with tracers in F flexibles, which undergoes tracer-based sorting to separate it into F and NF flexible fractions. The F fraction then undergoes delamination and deinking as the purification method (Loop 3) producing F laminate with 50% PCR for coffee pouches, while the NF fraction is processed through the CreaSolv® method (Loop 1) producing NF laminate with 52% PCR for detergent pouches.

Similarly, in the *Household F and NF Packaging - Cycle 2 - Loop 3 Cycle 2 and Loop 1*, the input from household waste is mixed EoL F and NF flexibles and tracers in F flexibles including PCR content, undergoing the same purification and production procedure as outlined above. In the *Household and Business waste, Baseline scenarios*, a fraction of 70% is directed to incineration with energy recovery, while the remaining fraction of 30% is sent to landfills (Eunomia & Plastic Recyclers Europe, 2020; Plastic Europe, 2022). The resulting outputs comprise the generation of electricity and heat from incineration.

In the NF pellet scenario - Loop 1, household PE-rich flexible packaging waste undergoes the CreaSolv® purification method producing non-food grade rPE pellet specifically designed for flexible packaging applications. In the F pellet scenario - Loop 3, household PE-rich flexible packaging waste is first sorted using tracer-based sorting to isolate F flexibles from NF flexibles. The F fraction then undergoes delamination and deinking for purification producing food-grade rPE pellets suitable for flexible packaging applications. In the Baseline pellet scenario, virgin (fossil-based) raw materials are utilized to manufacture vPE pellets, catering to both non-food (NF) and food (F) flexible packaging applications.

Furthermore, the data collection according to the scenarios was done in close cooperation with the project partners per process step: (1) Collection, SoA sorting and Tracer-based sorting, (2) Pretreatment including Oversorting, Shredding, Washing, Grinding, Float-sink separation, (3) Purification for option A-CreaSolv® and option B-Deinking and Delamination, (4) Posttreatment consisting of Recompounding and Deodorization, (5) Laminate production including film production and printing, (6) Ink production and Primer production, (7) Tracer production and (8) F and NF packaging production. The data collection templates for LCA, LCC and S-LCA data inventory were created and distributed by UGENT. These tables were completed by the respective partners to obtain the primary data for the final assessment, additional information was retrieved from the literature as secondary data if necessary.

The next step involves addressing certain data gaps to complete the final environmental, economic, and social impact assessment (LCSA) (Deliverable 7.5), facilitating a comprehensive analysis to identify system hotspots, compare recycling processes, and determine the most sustainable option. Key aspects requiring attention regarding data requirements and data confidentiality are included in Table 8.

Table 8: Key aspects requiring attention regarding data requirements and confidential data; this list is not exhaustive, but captures the primary areas of concern

Organization	Data Requirements	Confidential Data
Amcor	Laminate cost estimation for innovative triplex and duplex structures	-Energy data -Heat protective lacquer (OPV) costs ¹²
	Utility costs data (currently secondary sources)	
	SiOx price	
	R&D expenses and gross profit figures for the social indicator for R&D, safety training numbers to be validated by HR	
	Dimensional specifications of the packaging design, including mass-balance information	
Siegwerk	-	R&D expenses and gross profit data pertinent to the social indicator regarding R&D
Poly	-	LCA and LCC inventory and S-LCA data on GP and R&D budget
Siegwerk and Poly	Discussion on ink including tracer pricing	-
Nestle	All LCC data needs to be provided.	-
SUEZ	-	S-LCA inventory
IVV	-	LCA solvent data
UGENT	-	LCA inventory

¹² Heat protective lacquer (OPV) costs underly a bilateral NDA between AMCOR and SIEGWERK

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ANNEX

Table 9 presents the data collection template for the Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA) (part 2), focusing on the data inventory. The information is provided divided into parameters for general information and per social indicators. The key performance indicators (KPI) serve as the unit of measurement. It does not include the additional remarks column and category section to distinguish between obligatory and additional information. Only obligatory information is presented in the S-LCA data inventory in the Annex.

Table 9: Data collection template for Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA) part 2 (data inventory)

Indicator	Parameter	Data	KPI
General Information	Total number of employees (FTE)		Number of employees per company (FTE)
	Total number of production employee (FTE)		Number of employees per company and category (FTE)
	Total number of non-production production employee (FTE)		Number of employees per company and category (FTE)
	Total number of employees (head count)		Number of employees per company (head count)
	Total number of production employee (head count)		Number of employees per company and category (head count)
	Total number of non-production production employee (head count)		Number of employees per company and category (head count)
Existence of record of proof of age	Record of proof of age		Number of records per 1000 employees in the company/y
Existence of certified environmental management system (EMS)	EMAS certified EMS exists		Category per company/y
	ISO 14001:2015 certified EMS exists		Category per company/y
	EMS according to ISO 14001:2015 with internal auditing regime according to ISO 19011:2011 and/or Certified Environmental Management Officer exists		Category per company/y
	Outdated EMS according to ISO 14001:2004 exists		Category per company/y
Percentage of workers who are paid a living wage or above	Number of employees paid in category A Living Wage - Standard family, upper bound per company /y		Number of employees per company and category
	Number of employees paid in category B Living Wage - Standard family, lower bound per company /y		Number of employees per company and category
	Number of employees paid in category C Living Wage - Single adult, upper bound per company /y		Number of employees per company and category
	Number of employees paid in category D Living Wage - Single adult, lower bound per company /y		Number of employees per company and category
	Number of employees paid a minimum wage per company /y		Number of employees per company and category

Percentage of (fatal and non-fatal) accidents/injuries in the organization	Non-fatal accidents	Number of non-fatal accidents per 1000 employees in the company/y
	Fatal accidents	Number of fatal accidents per 1000 employees in the company/y
Existence of research and development (R&D)	Research and development department exists	y/n
	Gross profit (GP)	Gross profit (GP)/y
	R&D expenses	€/ y
Extent of safety training	Average hours of training on occupational health and safety per employee in the company/y	h/y and employee
	How training needs are assessed:	Qualitative description
	How the training is designed and delivered, including the content or topics addressed:	Qualitative description
	The competency of trainers:	Qualitative description
	Which workers receive the training:	Qualitative description
	The frequency of the training:	Qualitative description
	Whether the training is provided in a language easily understood by workers:	y/n
	Whether the training is provided free of charge and during paid working hours – if not	y/n
	Whether it is mandatory for workers to attend	y/n
	Whether they are compensated for this	y/n
	How the effectiveness of the training is evaluated:	Qualitative description
	Total number of training hours for total number of employees	Total number of training hours provided to employees
	Total number of training hours for production employees	Total number of training hours provided to production employee
	Total number of training hours non-production employees	Total number of training hours provided to non-production employee
Existence of health risk assessments regarding toxicity	Health risk assessments regarding toxicity exists	yes/ n.a./ no
Percentage of male/female employees	Male employees	Number of employees (FTE)
	Female employees	Number of employees (FTE)
	Other employees	Number of employees (FTE)
	Not disclosed employees	Number of employees (FTE)
	Male full-time employees	Number of full-time employees (FTE)
	Female full-time employees	Number of full-time employees (FTE)
	Other full-time employees	Number of full-time employees (FTE)
	Not disclosed full-time employees	Number of full-time employees (FTE)
	Male part-time employees	Number of part-time employees (FTE)
	Female part-time employees	Number of part-time employees (FTE)

	Other part-time employees		Number of part-time employees (FTE)
	Not disclosed part-time employees		Number of part-time employees (FTE)
	Male employees		Number of non-guaranteed hours employees (FTE)
	Female employees		Number of non-guaranteed hours employees (FTE)
	Other employees		Number of non-guaranteed hours employees (FTE)
	Not disclosed employees		Number of non-guaranteed hours employees (FTE)
Existence of extended producer responsibility (EPR) policy	Extended producer responsibility (EPR) policy exists		yes/ n.a./ no
Existence of formal policy against discrimination	Formal policy against discrimination exists		y/n
	Total number of incidents of discrimination during the reporting period.		Number of incidents / reporting period
	Does the formal policy include the following 4 step action plan against discrimination:		y/n
	1. Incident reviewed by the organization		
	2. Remediation plans being implemented		
	3. Remediation plans that have been implemented, with results reviewed through routine internal management review processes		
	4. Incident no longer subject to action.		

Collection and SoA sorting and Pretreatment-SUEZ

LCA data inventory

Loop 1

Table 10: Loop 1 Collection and SoA sorting and Pretreatment data inventory sheet

Process 1						
Collection at consumer	Inputs	Quantity per ton	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	Share of PE per Household yellow bin	1	ton		aha_allocation applied, bid with sophie, bang, SUEZ	own calculation_aha
	Household yellow bin or yellow bag (plastic packaging not only) waste	58	ton		aha_amount needed for providing 1 ton of PE flexible	FRAN Luc Billard at meeting 11/10/22
	Transport	434	km		aha_adjusted to 50:50 payload of 6 and 12 t per truck (57/12) lorry has to go ca. 4 times to provide 1 ton of PE flex, Distance consumer to sorting center 60km, Two different typ of payloads (1) 6t waste/ truck (2) 12t waste/ truck	
	Transport	269	km		aha_assumption 100% 12t payload	
	Transport	434	km		Assumption_aha: 50% 6t and 50% 12t; assumption_eks: 1/58 allocation applied for 1 ton of PE-rich flexible fraction	aha
	Outputs			Destination	Remarks	Source
	Household yellow bin or yellow bag (plastic packaging not only) waste	58	ton			own calculation_aha
Process 2						
SoA Sorting	Inputs	Quantity per ton	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	Household yellow bin or yellow bag (plastic packaging not only) waste	58	ton		aha_1,73% of 31000 is PE-flex	
	Electricity	53.00	kWh	grid France	3X 400 V, grid France	see LCI
	Diesel	1.14	l		forklift	see LCI
	Diesel	0.97	kg		forklift	
	Diesel combustion	43.40	MJ		incl. forklift as machinery	
	Bindingwie	1.29	kg			see LCI
	Outputs			Destination	Remarks	Source
	PE-rich flexibles/ Food and non-food	1.00	ton			see LCI
Process 3						
Transport to Pretreatment	Inputs	Quantity per ton	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	PE-rich flexibles/ Food and non-food	1	ton			
	Transport	200	km	EURO 6	16-32t	SUEZ
	Transport	200	tkm			eks own calculation
	Outputs			Destination	Remarks	Source
	PE-rich flexibles/ Food and non-food	1	ton			
Process 4						
Oversorting	Inputs	Quantity per ton	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	PE-rich flexibles/ Food and non-food	1	ton			
	Electricity	50	kWh		2 sorters + belts	
	Compressed air	200	m ³ /h			
	Outputs			Destination	Remarks	Source
	PE-rich flexibles	0.93	ton		Between 0,93 & 0,95	see LCI
		0.95	ton			
		0.94	ton		eks-own calculation average	
	Residue	Between 5% and	%		59% paper and carton, 20.2% unknown, 16% bottles and trays, 2.2% steel & aluminium, 2.2% tetrapack, 0.4% medical and hazardous waste	
	Residue to energy recovery	0.060	ton		eks-own calculation average	
		60.000	kg			
	59% paper and carton	0.0354	ton			
	20% unknown	0.01212	ton		Assumption_aha: negligible	
	16% bottles and trays	0.0096	ton		Assumption_aha: PET	
	2% steel aluminium	0.00132	ton		Assumption_aha: negligible	
	2% tetrapack	0.00132	ton		Assumption_aha: paper and carton	
	0% medical and hazardous waste	0.00034	ton			
	Transport to incineration	30.000	km		assumption_eks: 30 km	Hestin et al 2015
	Transport to incineration	1.800	tkm		assumption_eks: 10t lorry	Hestin et al 2015
Process 5						
Shredding	Inputs	Quantity per ton	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	PE-rich flexibles	0.94	ton		eks-rescaled for mass balance (see D43)	
	Electricity	169	kWh		eks-rescaled for mass balance (see D43)	
	Outputs			Destination	Remarks	Source
	PE-rich flakes	0.94	ton		eks-rescaled for mass balance (see D43)	
Process 6						
Washing	Inputs	Quantity per ton	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	PE-rich flakes	0.94	ton		losses are not evaluated per step but at the end of flo at sink separation/eks-rescaled for mass balance (see D43)	
	Electricity	35.156	kWh		2 friction washers	
	Water	0.392	m ³		Closed loop/eks-rescaled for mass balance	
	Outputs			Destination	Remarks	Source
	PE-rich flakes	0.94	ton		eks-rescaled for mass balance (see D43)	
	Wastewater	0.392	m ³		eks-rescaled for mass balance (see D43)	
	Wastewater	391.5	kg		Assumption_eks: negligible change of water density	
Process 7						
Grinding	Inputs	Quantity per ton	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	PE-rich flakes	0.94	ton		eks-rescaled for mass balance (see D43)	
	Electricity	66	kWh		1 equipment/eks-rescaled for mass balance	
	Outputs			Destination	Remarks	Source
	PE-rich flakes	0.94	ton		eks-rescaled for mass balance (see D43)	
Process 8						
Float-sink separation	Inputs	Quantity per ton	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	PE-rich flakes	0.94	ton		eks-rescaled for mass balance (see D43)	
	Electricity	18.8	kWh		2 floating tanks/eks-rescaled for mass balance (see D43)	
	Water	0.392	m ³ /h		Closed loop/eks-rescaled for mass balance	
	Outputs			Destination	Remarks	Source
	PE-rich flakes	0.921	ton			
	Residue	2%	%		rigid plastic, PVC, PA	
	Residue to energy recovery	0.02	ton/h			
	20% PET	0.00376	ton		Assumption_aha: equal share rigid plastic, PVC, PA	
	20% PP	0.00376	ton		Assumption_aha: equal share rigid plastic, PVC, PA	
	20% PS	0.00376	ton		Assumption_aha: equal share rigid plastic, PVC, PA	
	20% PA	0.00376	ton		Assumption_aha: equal share rigid plastic, PVC, PA	
	20% PVC/ PVDC	0.00376	ton		Assumption_aha: equal share rigid plastic, PVC, PA	
	Transport to incineration	30.000	km		assumption_eks: 30 km	Hestin et al 2015
	Transport to incineration	0.564	tkm		assumption_eks: 10t lorry	Hestin et al 2015
	Wastewater	0.392	m ³ /h		eks-rescaled for mass balance (see D43)	
	Wastewater	391.5	kg/h		Assumption_eks: negligible change of water density	
Process 9						
Waste water treatment	Inputs	Quantity per ton	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	Wastewater	0.783	m ³		20 m ³ per day/eks-rescaled for per hour and per ton	
		783.0	kg			
	Outputs			Destination	Remarks	Source
	Residue	N/A			please specify composition of residue e.g. 10% filter cake, 20% pulp	ecoinvent dataset
Transport (T)						
T1	Inputs	Transport mode	Unit	Truck technology	Remarks	Source
	Household plastic packaging waste	Lorry	km	EURO 6	6 to 12 tons, 60 km maximum	
		6 tons				12
		12 tons				6

Loop 2 Collection NESTLE

Table 11: Loop 2 Collection data inventory sheet

Process 1						
Collection at business	Inputs	Quantity per ton	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	Post-business PE-rich flexibles		1	ton		
	Transport Business -> DC		80	km	assumption based on input from NESTLE	
	Transport Business -> DC		80	tkm		
	Outputs	Quantity per ton	Unit	Destination	Remarks	Source
	Post-business PE-rich flexibles		1	ton		
Process 2						
Collection at distribution center (DC)	Inputs	Quantity per ton	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	Post-business PE-rich flexibles		1	ton		
	Transport DC-> SUEZ		100	km	assumption based on input from NESTLE	
	transport		100	tkm		
	Outputs	Quantity per ton	Unit	Destination	Remarks	Source
	Post-business PE-rich flexibles		1	ton		

Loop 2 Pretreatment SUEZ

Table 12: Loop 2 Pretreatment data inventory sheet

Process 1						
Oversorting	Inputs	Quantity per FU	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	PE-rich flexibles/ Food		1	ton		
	Electricity		50	kWh	2 sorters + belts+Speedair (TOMRA)	
	Compressed air		200	m3		
	Outputs	Quantity per FU	Unit	Destination	Remarks	Source
	PE-rich flexibles		0.98	ton		
	Residue to energy recovery		0.020	ton		see LCI_SUEZ Loop(1) G80
	59% paper and carton		0.0118	ton		
	20% unknown		0.00404	ton	Assumption_aha: negligible	
	16% bottles and trays		0.0032	ton	Assumption_aha: PET	
	2% steel & aluminium		0.00044	ton	Assumption_aha: negligible	
	2% tetrapack		0.00044	ton	Assumption_aha: paper and carton	
	0% medical and hazardous waste		0.00008	ton	Assumption_aha: negligible	
Process 2						
Shredding	Inputs	Quantity per FU	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	PE-rich flexibles		0.98	ton	aha-rescaled for mass balance (see D21)	
	Electricity		176	kWh	aha-rescaled for mass balance (see D21)	
	Outputs	Quantity per FU	Unit	Destination	Remarks	Source
	PE-rich flakes		0.98	ton	aha-rescaled for mass balance (see D21)	
Process 3						
Washing	Inputs	Quantity per FU	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	PE-rich flakes		0.98	ton	losses are not evaluated per step but at the end of float sink separation/eks-rescaled for mass balance (see D43)	
	Electricity		36.652	kWh	2 friction washers/eks-rescaled for mass balance (see D43)	
	Water		0.408	m3	Closed loop	
			408.2	kg		
	Outputs	Quantity per FU	Unit	Destination	Remarks	Source
	PE-rich flakes		0.98	ton	aha-rescaled for mass balance (see D21)	
	Wastewater		0.408	m3		
			408.17	kg	Assumption_eks: negligible change of water density	
Process 4						
Grinding	Inputs	Quantity per FU	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	PE-rich flakes		0.98	ton	aha-rescaled for mass balance (see D21)	
	Electricity		69	kWh	1 equipment	
	Outputs	Quantity per FU	Unit	Destination	Remarks	Source
	PE-rich flakes		0.98	ton	aha-rescaled for mass balance (see D21)	
Process 5						
Float-sink separation	Inputs	Quantity per FU	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	PE-rich flakes		0.98	ton	aha-rescaled for mass balance (see D21)	
	Electricity		19.6	kWh	2 floating tanks	
	Water		0.408	m3		
	Water		408.2	kg		
	Outputs	Quantity per FU	Unit	Destination	Remarks	Source
	PE-rich flakes		0.970	ton	aha-rescaled for mass balance (see D62)	
	Residue		1%	%	rigid plastic, PVC,PA	
	Residue to energy recovery		0.01	ton		
			9.80	kg		
	20% PET		0.00376	ton	Assumption_aha: equal share rigid plastic, PVC,PA	
	20% PP		0.00376	ton	Assumption_aha: equal share rigid plastic, PVC,PA	
	20% PS		0.00376	ton	Assumption_aha: equal share rigid plastic, PVC,PA	
	20% PA		0.00376	ton	Assumption_aha: equal share rigid plastic, PVC,PA	
	20% PVC / PVDC		0.00376	ton	Assumption_aha: equal share rigid plastic, PVC,PA	
	Wastewater		0.408	m3		
Process 6						
Waste water treatment	Inputs	Quantity per FU	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	Wastewater		0.812	m3	20 m3 per day	
	Wastewater		812.3	kg		
	Outputs	Quantity per FU	Unit	Destination	Remarks	Source
	Residue		N/A		please specify composition of residue e.g. 10% filter cake, 20% pulp	ecoinvent dataset

Loop 3 including Tracer-based sorting

Table 13: Loop 3 Collection and SoA sorting and Pretreatment data inventory sheet

Process 1						
Collection at consumer	Inputs	Quantity per tone	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	Share of PE per Household yellow bin	1.0	ton		aha_allocation applied, tbd with sophie, trang, SUEZ	
	Household yellow bin or yellow bag (plastic packaging not only) waste	57.8	ton		Assumption_eks: same amount as Loop 1	own calculation_aha
	Transport	433.8	km		aha_adjusted to 50:50 payload of 6 and 12t per truck (57/12t) lorry has to go ca. 4 times to provide 1 ton of PE flex, Distance consumer to sorting center 60 km, Two different typ of payloads (1) 6t waste/ truck (2) 12t waste/ truck	
	Transport	289.2	km		aha_assumption 100% 12t payload	JEAN Luc bilateral meeting 11/10/22
	Transport	433.8	tkm		Assumption_aha: 50% 6t and 50% 12t; assumption_eks: 1/58 allocation applied for 1 ton of PE-rich flexible fraction	aha
Outputs						
	Household yellow bin or yellow bag (plastic packaging)	57.8	ton			own calculation_aha
Process 2						
SoA Sorting	Inputs	Quantity per tone	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	Household plastic packaging waste	57.8	ton			
	Electricity	53.0	kWh	grid France	3X 400 V, grid France	
	Diesel	1.1	kg		forklift	
	Diesel combustion	43.4	MJ		incl. forklift as machinery	
	Binding wire	1.3	kg			
Outputs						
	PE-rich flexibles/ Food and non-food	1.0	ton			based on the annual 2021 production of the sorting center SUEZ at Poitiers
Process 3						
TBS Sorting	Inputs	Quantity per tone	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	PE-rich flexibles/ Food and non-food	1.0	ton			
	Electricity	confidential	kWh			Lars expert judgement WPL meeting 12.10.22
Outputs						
	PE-rich flexibles incl. Tracers/ f. Food	0.3	ton		assumption_eks: if all the food packaging already contains tracers	
	PE-rich non-f. flexibles	0.7	ton		assumption_eks: if all the food packaging already contains tracers please specify composition of residue e.g. 10% PP, 20% PEI	
	PE-rich Food flexibles	0.3	ton			
Process 4						
Transport to Pretreatment	Inputs	Quantity per tone	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	PE-rich flexibles/ Food	0.3	ton	EURO 6	16t-32t	SUEZ
	Transport	200.0	km	EURO 6	16t-32t	SUEZ
	Transport	50.9	tkm			eks own calculation
Outputs						
	PE-rich flexibles/ Food	0.3	ton			
Process 5						
Oversorting	Inputs	Quantity per tone	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	PE-rich flexibles/ Food	0.3	ton		eks-rescaled for mass balance (see D49)	
	Electricity	12.7	kWh		2 sorters + belts+Speedair (TOMRA)	
	Compressed air	50.9	m3/h			
Outputs						
	PE-rich flexibles	0.2	ton		eks-rescaled for mass balance (see D49)	
	Residue	0.0	ton		eks-rescaled for mass balance (see D49)	
	Residue to incineration	12.7	kg		eks-rescaled for mass balance (see D49)	
	59% paper and carton	0.0075	ton			
	20% unknown	0.0026	ton		Assumption_aha: negligible	
	16% bottles and trays	0.0026	ton		Assumption_aha: PET	
	2% steel/aluminium	0.0003	ton		Assumption_aha: negligible	
	2% tetrapack	0.0003	ton		Assumption_aha: paper and carton	
	Transport to incineration	30.0	km		assumption_eks: 30 km	Hestin et al 2015
	Transport to incineration	0.4	tkm		assumption_eks: 10t lorry	Hestin et al 2015
Process 6						
Shredding	Inputs	Quantity per tone	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	PE-rich flexibles	0.2	ton		eks-rescaled for mass balance (see D49)	
	Electricity	43.5	kWh		1 equipment / eks-rescaled for mass balance (see D49)	
Outputs						
	PE-rich flakes	0.2	ton			
Process 7						
Washing	Inputs	Quantity per tone	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	PE-rich flakes incl. Tracers/ f. Food	0.2	ton			
	Electricity	9.0	kWh		2 friction washers / eks-rescaled for mass balance (see D49)	
	Water	0.1	m3/h		eks-rescaled for mass balance	
	Water	100.8	kg			
Outputs						
	PE-rich flakes incl. Tracers/ f. Food	0.2	ton			
	Wastewater	0.1	m3/h		eks-rescaled for mass balance	
Process 8						
Grinding	Inputs	Quantity per tone	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	PE-rich flakes incl. Tracers/ f. Food	0.2	ton			
	Electricity	16.9	kWh		1 equipment	
Outputs						
	PE-rich flakes incl. Tracers/ f. Food	0.2	ton			
Process 9						
Float-sink separation	Inputs	Quantity per tone	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	PE-rich flakes incl. Tracers/ f. Food	0.2	ton			
	Electricity	4.8	kWh		2 floating tanks	
	Water	0.1	m3/h		eks-rescaled for mass balance	
	Water	100.8	kg			
Outputs						
	PE-rich flakes incl. Tracers/ f. Food	0.2	ton			
	Residue	0.002	ton/h		rigid plastic, PVC/PA	
	Residue to energy recovery	0.005	ton/h			
	20% PEI	0.001	ton			
	20% PP	0.001	ton		Assumption_aha: equal share rigid plastic, PVC/PA	
	20% PS	0.001	ton		Assumption_aha: equal share rigid plastic, PVC/PA	
	20% PA	0.001	ton		Assumption_aha: equal share rigid plastic, PVC/PA	
	20% PVC/ PVDc	0.001	ton		Assumption_aha: equal share rigid plastic, PVC/PA	
	Transport to incineration	30.0	km		assumption_eks: 30 km	Hestin et al 2015
	Transport to incineration	0.1	tkm		assumption_eks: 10t lorry	Hestin et al 2015
	Wastewater	0.1	m3/h		eks-rescaled for mass balance	
Process 10						
Waste water treatment	Inputs	Quantity per tone	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	Wastewater	0.2	m3/h		20 m3 per day/eks-rescaled for per hour and per ton	
Outputs						
	Residue	NA	NA		please specify composition of residue e.g. 10% filter cake, 20% pulp	ecoinvent dataset
Transport (T)						
T1	Inputs	Transport mode	Unit	Truck technology	Remarks	Source
	Household plastic packaging waste	Lorry	km	EURO 6	please specify truck payload e.g. 3.5t-7.5t; 7.5t-16t; 16t-32t; >32t	
			6 tons			6
			12 tons			12
T2	Inputs	Transport mode	Unit	Truck technology	Remarks	Source
	PE-rich flakes incl. Tracers/ f. Food	Lorry	km	EURO 6	please specify truck payload e.g. 3.5t-7.5t; 7.5t-16t; 16t-32t; >32t	
			200.0		16t-32t	SUEZ

LCC data inventory SoA sorting and Pretreatment

Table 14: LCC data inventory SoA sorting SUEZ, sce. = service, pc. = piece

CAPEX, OPEX, Revenues					
Type of cost	Cost points	Quantity (w/o depreciation)	Unit	Remarks	Source
<i>Capital costs</i>					
Additional cost	Buildings/property [Building construction (BC)]	15 000 000	€/pc.	Depreciation of the whole process line on 20 years	Email Jean-Luc 30.11.2022; meeting Jean-Luc 05.12.2022
Primary cost	Equipment [Price of Equipment (PC)]	10 000 000	€/pc.	Depreciation of the whole process line on 7 years	Email Jean-Luc 30.11.2022; meeting Jean-Luc 05.12.2023
Additional cost	Installation and running test (IC)	6 000 000	€/sce.	60% of PC depreciated on 7 years	(Bashirgonbadi et al., 2022)
Additional cost	Engineering and project management (EPMC)	1 600 000	€/sce.	10% of PC and 10% of IC depreciated on 7 years	(Bashirgonbadi et al., 2022)
<i>Operational costs</i>					
Personnel	Salary and wages [Labor cost]	50 000	€/person.year	1 person/ktpa	SUEZ
	Industrial intermediate goods (Binding wire)	0.66	€/ kg	assumption_aha: binding wire price alibaba US\$720/t	Alibaba.com (2023)
Utility costs	Fuel	1.66	€/ kg; l		SUEZ
Material costs	Freshwater	1	€/ m3	NA, no water input in SoA sorting	SUEZ
Utility costs	Electricity	0.077	€/ kWh	for a plant in France	SUEZ
Other operational costs	Maintenance and repairs	1 304 000	€/pc. and sce.	4% * CAPEX	(Bashirgonbadi et al., 2022); (Cimpan et al., 2022); (Cimpan et al., 2016; Larrain et al., 2021)
Other operational costs	Insurance	228 200	€/pc. and sce.	0.7% * CAPEX	(Bashirgonbadi et al., 2022); (Cimpan et al., 2016; Larrain et al., 2021)
Other operational costs	General expenses	209 856	€/year	10% of total operational cost	(Bashirgonbadi et al., 2022); (Cimpan et al., 2016; Larrain et al., 2021)
EoL [Disposal fee]	Fee landfilling	160	€/t	NA, no landfilling [paid for refused waste (residue) for disposal or incineration]	SUEZ
EoL [Disposal fee]	Fee incineration	120	€/t		SUEZ
<i>Revenues/ Positive Cash flows</i>					
Selling of products	Product	n.a.	€/ product	Market prices for secondary products	
	Co-product	n.a.	€/ product	Market prices for secondary products	
	Subsidies	n.a.	€/ year	e.g for setting up a waste recycling mangement system	

Table 15: LCC data inventory Pretreatment SUEZ

CAPEX, OPEX, Revenues					
Type of cost	Cost points	Quantity (w/o depreciation)	Unit	Remarks	Source
<i>Capital costs</i>					
Additional cost	Buildings/property [Building construction (BC)]	2 175 000	€/pc.	Depreciation of the whole process line on 20 years	Email Jean-Luc 30.11.2022; meeting Jean-Luc 05.12.2022
Primary cost	Equipment [Price of Equipment (PC)]	1 450 000	€/pc.	Depreciation of the whole process line on 7 years	Email Jean-Luc 30.11.2022; meeting Jean-Luc 05.12.2023
Additional cost	Installation and running test (IC)	870 000	€/sce.	60% of PC depreciated on 7 years	(Bashirgonbadi et al., 2022)
Additional cost	Engineering and project management (EPMC)	232 000	€/sce.	10% of PC and 10% of IC depreciated on 7 years	(Bashirgonbadi et al., 2022)
<i>Operational costs</i>					
Personnel	Salary and wages [Labor cost]	50 000	€/person.year	1,5 person/ktpa	SUEZ
Utility costs	Fuel	1.66	€/ l	NA, no fuel input for pretreatment	SUEZ
Material costs	Freshwater	1	€/ m3		SUEZ
Utility costs	Electricity	0.077	€/ kWh	for a plant in France	SUEZ
Other operational costs	Maintenance and repairs	189 080	€/pc. and sce.	4% * CAPEX	(Bashirgonbadi et al., 2022); (Cimpan et al., 2016; Larrain et al., 2021)
Other operational costs	Insurance	32 365	€/pc. and sce.	0.7% * CAPEX	(Bashirgonbadi et al., 2022); (Cimpan et al., 2016; Larrain et al., 2021)
Other operational costs	General expenses	52 045	€/year	10% of total operational cost	(Bashirgonbadi et al., 2022); (Cimpan et al., 2016; Larrain et al., 2021)
EoL [Disposal fee]	Fee landfilling	160	€/t	NA, no landfilling [paid for refused waste (residue) for disposal or incineration]	SUEZ
EoL [Disposal fee]	Fee incineration	120	€/t		SUEZ
	Wastewater treatment	0.500	€/ m3	assumption aha_ based on literature for Spain 2019	Moral Pajares et al., 2019
<i>Revenues/ Positive Cash flows</i>					
Selling of products	Product	n.a.	€/ product	Market prices for secondary products	
	Co-product	n.a.	€/ product	Market prices for secondary products	
	Subsidies	n.a.	€/ year	e.g for setting up a waste recycling mangement system	

S-LCA data inventory

The S-LCA data inventory for SoA sorting and Pretreatment by SUEZ is considered confidential and is shared exclusively within the project consortium.

Purification option A CreaSolv® -IVV

LCA data inventory

Loops 1-3

Table 16: Loops 1-3 Purification option A CreaSolv® data inventory sheet (data on solvent is confidential)

Process 1						
Continuous dissolving	Inputs	Quantity per kg PE Output	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	PE-rich flakes	1.11	kg		Calculation for 10.000 t/a plant; not yet a definite mass balance for current input (PE)	
	Electricity	0.45	kWh			
	Heat	2.38	MJ		please specify source of heat e.g. natural gas	
	Recovered solvent	confidential	kg		Regarding the solvent, we cannot give more information on the formulation due to confidentiality arrangements.	
	Virgin solvent	0.01	kg		Maximum solvent loss (<0,1%) that has to be compensated. Rest is always kept in cycle	
	Outputs	Quantity per kg	Unit	Destination	Remarks	Source
	PE solution (incl. Residues)	13.32	kg			
Process 2						
Multistage filtration	Inputs	Quantity per kg	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	PE solution (incl. Residues)	13.32	kg			
	Electricity	0.18	kWh			
	Heat	0.32	MJ		please specify source of heat e.g. natural gas	
	Outputs	Quantity per kg	Unit	Destination	Remarks	Source
	Filtered PE solution	13.12	kg			
	Residue including PE solution on surface	0.21	kg		includes residue of Process 3.2.1, processes are interlinked with each other, ev. Split 80:20	
Process 3						
Residual treatment and PE purification	Inputs	Quantity per kg	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	Residue including PE solution on surface	0.11	kg			
	Electricity	0.55	kWh			
	Heat	2.85	MJ			
Process 3.1						
Washing + Drying of the residual fraction	Inputs	Quantity per kg	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	Residue including PE solution on surface	0.21	kg		30% PP, 20% PA, 10% PET	
	Electricity	included in 3	kg			
	Heat	included in 3	kg		please specify source of heat e.g. natural gas	
	Washing solution/Solvent	confidential	kg		Regarding the solvent, we cannot give more information on the formulation due to confidentiality arrangements.	update on process flow scheme, washing solution is recovered solvent, meeting 25.04 Matthias
	Outputs	Quantity per kg	Unit	Destination	Remarks	Source
	Washed Residue including solvent on the surface	0.20	kg			
Process 3.1.1						
Drying residual fraction	Inputs	Quantity per kg	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	Washed Residue including solvent on the surface	0.20	kg		30% PP, 12% PA, 8% PET (50% residue) rest (50% solvent) based on FR fraction	
	Electricity	included in 3	kg			
	Heat	included in 3	kg		please specify source of heat e.g. natural gas	
	Outputs	Quantity per kg	Unit	Destination	Remarks	Source
	Dried residue	0.10	kg		assumption_eks: 60% PP, 24% PA, 16% PET	
	60% PP	0.06	kg			
	24% PA	0.02	kg			
	16% PET	0.02	kg			
	Transport to incineration	30.000	km		assumption_eks: 30 km	Hestin et al 2015
	Transport to incineration	0.003	tkm		assumption_eks: 10t lorry	Hestin et al 2015
Process 3.2						
PE purification	Inputs	Quantity per kg	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	Filtered PE solution	13.12	kg			
	Removed PE solution	0.11	kg			update 28.04 Matthias
	Electricity	included in 3	kg			
	Heat	included in 3	kg		please specify source of heat e.g. natural gas	
	Recovered purification agent	confidential	kg		Regarding the purification agent, we cannot give more information on the formulation and amount due to confidentiality arrangements.	100% recovery 19.1 meeting Matthias
	Outputs	Quantity per kg	Unit	Destination	Remarks	Source
	Purified PE solution	13.21	kg			
Process 3.2.1						
Removal of fine residues and separation of solvent & purification agent	Inputs	Quantity per kg	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	Purified PE solution	13.23	kg			
	Electricity	included in 3	kg			
	Heat	included in 3	kg		please specify source of heat e.g. natural gas	
	Outputs	Quantity per kg	Unit	Destination	Remarks	Source
	Purified PE solution	13.21	kg			
	Fine residues	0.010	kg			update 28.04 Matthias
	Solvent loss over fine residues	confidential	kg			update 28.04 Matthias
	Transport to incineration	30	km		assumption_eks: 30 km	Hestin et al 2015
	Transport to incineration	0.0005	tkm		assumption_eks: 10t lorry	Hestin et al 2015
Process 4						
Multiple stage drying	Inputs	Quantity per kg	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	PE solution + removed PE solution from residue	13.21	kg			
	Electricity	1.25	kWh			
	Heat	2.38	MJ		please specify source of heat e.g. natural gas	
	Outputs	Quantity per kg	Unit	Destination	Remarks	Source
	PE melt	1	kg			
	Remaining solvent	confidential	kg			update 28.04 Matthias
	Recovered solvent	confidential	kg			
Process 5						
Regranulation/-compounding	Inputs	Quantity per kg	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	PE melt	1	kg			
	Electricity	0.05	kWh			
	Heat	0.0	MJ		please specify source of heat e.g. natural gas	
	Outputs	Quantity per kg	Unit	Destination	Remarks	Source
	PE PCR pellets	1	kg		PE PCR pellets consist of 1 kg PE and 0,001 kg Solvent	update 28.04 Matthias
Auxiliary (process 1-5)						
	Nitrogen	0.04	Nm ³		Nitrogen forms an airtight protective atmosphere	update 28.04 Matthias
	Nitrogen	0.05	kg			

LCC data inventory

Table 17: LCC data inventory Purification option A CreaSolv® IVV

CAPEX, OPEX, Revenues					
Type of cost	Cost points	Quantity	Unit	Remarks	Source
<i>Capital costs</i>					
Investment	Buildings/property [Building construction (BC)]	1 000 000	€	Industrial plant, overall size, not depreciated over 20 year	
Primary cost	Equipment [Price of Equipment (PC)]	3 445 209	€	depreciation of machinery, initial utilities (solvent, HTM, etc.) per year , depreciation over 7 years	IVV, own calculations
	Installation and running test (IC)	2 067 125	€	60% of PC depreciated on 7 years	(Bashirgonbadi et al., 2022)
	Engineering and project management (EPMC)	551 233	€	10% of PC and 10% of IC depreciated on 7 years	(Bashirgonbadi et al., 2022)
<i>General Dates</i>					
Annual operating hours		7 201	h/a	estimated operating hours	
<i>Operational costs</i>					
Personnel	Salary and wages	800 400	€/a	Overall staff working in 4 shifts	IVV, own calculations
Material costs	Input material	106	€/t	waste fraction (pos. not applying to 310 fraction); including pretreatment	IVV, supplier
Material costs	Utilities e.g. nitrogen	409 850	€/a	covers all the materials used per ton of waste input	IVV, experience
Utility costs	Electricity	230	€/ MWh	Year 2022 (September)	
Utility costs	Heat	100	€/MWh	Year 2022 (September)	
Waste related costs	Residue disposal costs	20	€/ t	cost of disposal of ridues of the process	
Other operational costs	Quality assurance	100 000	€/year		
Other operational costs	Maintenance and repairs	315 930	€/year		
Other operational costs	Taxes	65 705	€/year	annual increase of 1% on profit	
Other operational costs	Insurance	353 497	€/year		
<i>Revenues/ Positive Cash flows</i>					
Selling of products	Product	2	€/ kg product	Daily market price for virgin PE-LD	
	Co-product	n.a.	€/ product	Market prices for secondary products	
	Subsidies	n.a.	€/ year	e.g for setting up a waste recycling mangement system	

S-LCA data inventory

The S-LCA data inventory for CreaSolv® by IVV is based on information from SUEZ which is considered confidential and is shared exclusively within the project consortium.

Purification option B Delamination and Deinking-UGENT

LCA data inventory

Loop 2-3

The LCA data inventory for Delamination and Deinking is considered confidential and is shared exclusively within the project consortium.

S-LCA data inventory

The S-LCA data inventory for Delamination and Deinking by UGENT is based on information from SUEZ which is considered confidential and is shared exclusively within the project consortium.

LCC data inventory

Table 18: LCC data inventory Purification option B Delamination and Deinking UGENT

CAPEX, OPEX, Revenues					
Type of cost	Cost points	Quantity	Unit	Remarks	Source
<i>Capital costs</i>					
	Buildings/property	1 058 347	€/pc.	59% of PC	own calculations based on (Bashirgonbadi et al., 2022): Expert judgment and (Cimpan et al., 2016; Larrain et al., 2021, 2020; Sinnott and Towler, 2019)
	Equipment/software	1 804 000	€/pc.	Assumption_aha based on UGEnt meeting WP7 01.23; Cold washing unit, Depreciation of the whole process line on 7 years (Irdanto)	(Bashirgonbadi et al., 2022)
	Installation and running test (IC)	1 082 400	€/pc.	60% of PC depreciated on 7 years	(Bashirgonbadi et al., 2022)
	Engineering and project management (EPMC)	288 640	€/pc.	10% of PC and 10% of IC depreciated on 7 years	(Bashirgonbadi et al., 2022)
<i>Operational costs</i>					
Personnel	Salary and wages	50 000	€/year	1,5 person/ktpa	SUEZ
Material costs	Raw materials	0.106	€/ kg	Mix of flexible packaging waste; assumption eks: make same as IVV input	IVV
Material costs	Solvent	10	€/kg	10 € per kg	SIEGWERK
Material costs	Freshwater	1	€/ m3; l		SUEZ
Utility costs	Electricity	0.0770	€/ kWh	for a plant in France	SUEZ
Utility costs	Heat	0.0432	€/ kWh	assumption_eks: using 2021 data, as 2022 data surged due to Ukraine war	EUROSTAT
Material costs	Solvent makeup cost	4	€/kg	as per Martijn email 18.04.23	Cavaignac et al., 2021
Other operational costs	Maintenance and repairs	169 335	€/year	assumption_eks: 4% of CAPEX	(Bashirgonbadi et al., 2022): (Cimpan et al., 2016; Larrain et al., 2021)
Other operational costs	Insurance	29 634	€/year	assumption_eks: 0.7% of CAPEX	(Bashirgonbadi et al., 2022): (Cimpan et al., 2016; Larrain et al., 2021)
EOI	Fee landfilling	160	€/t	paid for refused waste (residue) for disposal or incineration	SUEZ
EOI	Fee incineration	120	€/t		SUEZ
<i>Revenues/ Positive Cash flows</i>					
Selling of products	Product	2	€/ kg product	assumption_eks: same as IVV output	
	Co-product	n.a.	€/ product	Market prices for secondary products	
	Subsidies	n.a.	€/ year	e.g for setting up a waste recycling management system	

Recompounding-SUEZ

LCA data inventory

Loop 2-3

Table 19: Loop 2-3 Recompounding data inventory sheet

Process 1						
Preconditioning	Inputs	Quantity per tone	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	Pretreated PE flakes	1	Ton/h			
	Electricity	17	kWh		storage silo above the agglomerator, belt conveyor, 400 V	
Outputs						
	PE flakes	1	ton		assumption_eks: loss happens here, according to schematic diagram	
Process 2						
Melting	Inputs	Quantity per tone	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	PE flakes	1	ton		assumption_eks: loss happens here, according to schematic diagram	
	Electricity	550	kWh		including agglomerator, extruder, 400 V	
Outputs						
	PE flakes	1	ton		assumption_eks: loss happens here, according to schematic diagram	
Process 3						
Filtration	Inputs	Quantity per tone	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	PE flakes	1	ton		assumption_eks: loss happens here, according to schematic diagram	
	Electricity	26	kWh		400 V	
Outputs						
	PE flakes	0.95	ton		assumption_eks: loss happens here, according to schematic diagram	
	Residue	0.050	ton		assumption_eks: polymers with higher melting temp than PO (PET, PA, PVC, PS)	
		50.000	kg			
	25% PET	0.013	ton		assumption_eks: equal distribution of PET, PA, PVC, PS	
	25% PA	0.013	ton		assumption_eks: equal distribution of PET, PA, PVC, PS	
	25% PVC	0.013	ton		assumption_eks: equal distribution of PET, PA, PVC, PS	
	25% PS	0.013	ton		assumption_eks: equal distribution of PET, PA, PVC, PS	
	Transport to incineration	30.000	km		assumption_eks: 30 km	Hestin et al 2015
	Transport to incineration	1.500	tkm		assumption_eks: 10t lorry	Hestin et al 2015
Process 4						
Final degassing	Inputs	Quantity per tone	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	PE flakes	0.95	ton		assumption_eks: loss happens here, according to schematic diagram	
	Electricity	5	kWh		400 V	
Outputs						
	PE flakes	1	ton		assumption_eks: loss happens here, according to schematic diagram	
Process 5						
Homogenisation	Inputs	Quantity per tone	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	PE flakes	0.95	ton		assumption_eks: loss happens here, according to schematic diagram	
	Electricity	15	kWh		400 V, mixing silo after the pelletizing	
Outputs						
	PE flakes	1	ton		assumption_eks: loss happens here, according to schematic diagram	
Process 6						
Pelletizing	Inputs	Quantity per tone	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	PE flakes	0.95	Ton/h		assumption_eks: loss happens here, according to schematic diagram	
	Electricity	21	kWh		including a blower for transferring granules to mixing silo. Usually, the pelletizing is done before the homogenisation	
	Electricity	5	kWh		Big bag filling station	
Outputs						
	PE PCR pellets	0.95	ton		assumption_eks: loss happens here, according to schematic diagram	
Transport (T)						
T1	Inputs	Transport mode	Unit	Truck technology	Remarks	Source
	PE flakes	Lorry	km	EURO 5	please specify truck payload e.g. 3,5t-7,5t; 7,5t-16t; 16t-32t; >32t	
T2	Inputs	Transport mode	Unit	Truck technology	Remarks	Source
	PE PCR pellets	Lorry	km	EURO 5	please specify truck payload e.g. 3,5t-7,5t; 7,5t-16t; 16t-32t; >32t	

LCC data inventory

Table 20: LCC data inventory Recompounding SUEZ

CAPEX, OPEX, Revenues					
Type of cost	Cost points	Quantity	Unit	Remarks	Source
<i>Capital costs</i>					
	Buildings/property	86 827	€/year	59% of PC	own calculations based on (Bashirgonbadi et al., 2022): Expert judgment and (Cimpan et al., 2016; Larrain et al., 2021, 2020; Sinnott and Towler, 2019)
	Equipment/software	148 000	€/year	1 035 000 €, depreciation on 7 years	
	Installation and running test (IC)	88 800	€/year	60% of PC depreciated on 7 years	
	Engineering and project management (EPMC)	23 680	€/year	10% of PC and 10% of IC depreciated on 7 years	
<i>Operational costs</i>					
Personnel	Salary and wages	50 000	€/year	assumption_eks: 1.5 person/ktpa	
Utility costs	Freshwater	1	€/ m3		
Utility costs	Electricity	0.077	€/ kWh		
Other operational costs	Maintenance and repairs	13 892	€/year	8 % of the capex	
Other operational costs	Insurance	2 431	€/year	1 % of the capex	
EoL	Fee landfilling	160	€/t		
EoL	Fee incineration	120	€/t		
Other operational costs	General expenses	40 693	€/year	10% of total operational cost	(Bashirgonbadi et al., 2022); (Cimpan et al., 2016; Larrain et al., 2021)
<i>Revenues/ Positive Cash flows</i>					
Selling of products	Product	900	€/ton		
	Co-product	n.a	€/ product	Market prices for secondary products	
	Subsidies	n.a	€/ year	e.g for setting up a waste recycling mangement system	

S-LCA data inventory

The S-LCA data inventory for Recompounding by SUEZ is considered confidential and is shared exclusively within the project consortium.

Deodorization-KREYEN

LCA data inventory

Loop 1

Table 21: Loop 1 Deodorization data inventory sheet, confidential process engineering data e.g. air for cooling

Process 1						
Infrared treatment	Inputs	Quantity per year	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	PE PCR pellets	1 000	kg			
	Air for cooling	confidential			process engineering data are not published	
	Heat via electricity	60	kWh		high voltage, Energy Consumption is an estimated value and depends on material and processdesign	
	specific energie consumption	60	Wh		specific energie consumption strongly depends on Material and processdesign	
		0.06	kWh			
	Outputs	Quantity per year	Unit	Destination	Remarks	Source
	PE PCR pellets	1 000	kg		Output = input	
	Air emissions (VOC)	819 540	ug		assumption_eks: 50% from initial VOC removed in infrared treatment and 50% in thermal treatment	
		0.00082	kg			
Process 2						
Thermal treatment	Inputs	Quantity per year	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	PE PCR pellets	1 000	kg			
	Air	confidential			process engineering data are not published	
	Heat via electricity	25	kWh		high voltage, Energy Consumption is an estimated value and depends on material and processdesign	
	specific energie consumption	25	Wh		specific energie consumption strongly depends on Material and processdesign	
		0.03	kWh			
	Outputs	Quantity per year	Unit	Destination	Remarks	Source
	PE PCR pellets deodorized	1 000	kg			
	Air emissions (VOC)	819 540	ug		assumption_eks: 50% from initial VOC removed in infrared treatment and 50% in thermal treatment	
		0.00082	kg			
Transport (T)						
T1 (upstream)	Inputs	Transport mode	Unit	Truck technology	Remarks	Source
	PE PCR pellets	Lorry	km	EURO 5	please specify truck payload e.g. 3,5t-7,5t; 7,5t-16t, 16t-32t, >32t	
T2 (downstream)	Inputs	Transport mode	Unit	Truck technology	Remarks	Source
	PE PCR pellets deodorized	Lorry	km	EURO 5	please specify truck payload e.g. 3,5t-7,5t; 7,5t-16t, 16t-32t, >32t	

Loop 2-3

Table 22: Loop 2-3 Deodorization data inventory sheet, confidential process engineering data e.g. air for cooling

Process 1						
Infrared treatment	Inputs	Quantity per year	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	PE PCR pellets	1 000	kg			
	Air for cooling	confidential			process engineering data are not published	
	Heat via electricity	60	kWh		high voltage, Energy Consumption is an estimated value and depends on material and processdesign	
	specific energie consumption	60	Wh		specific energie consumption strongly depends on Material and processdesign	
		0.06	kWh			
	Outputs	Quantity per year	Unit	Destination	Remarks	Source
	PE PCR pellets	1 000	kg		Output = input	
	Air emissions (VOC) - Food	1 598 538	ug		assumption_eks: 50% from initial VOC removed in infrared treatment and 50% in thermal treatment	
		0.00160	kg			
Process 2						
Thermal treatment	Inputs	Quantity per year	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	PE PCR pellets	1 000	kg			
	Air	confidential			process engineering data are not published	
	Heat via electricity	25	kWh		high voltage, Energy Consumption is an estimated value and depends on material and processdesign	
	specific energie consumption	25	Wh		specific energie consumption strongly depends on Material and processdesign	
		0.03	kWh			
	Outputs	Quantity per year	Unit	Destination	Remarks	Source
	PE PCR pellets deodorized	1 000	kg			
	Air emissions (VOC) - Food	1 598 538	ug		assumption_eks: 50% from initial VOC removed in infrared treatment and 50% in thermal treatment	
		0.00160	kg			
Transport (T)						
T1 (upstream)	Inputs	Transport mode	Unit	Truck technology	Remarks	Source
	PE PCR pellets	Lorry	km	EURO 5	please specify truck payload e.g. 3,5t-7,5t; 7,5t-16t, 16t-32t, >32t	
T2 (downstream)	Inputs	Transport mode	Unit	Truck technology	Remarks	Source
	PE PCR pellets deodorized	Lorry	km	EURO 5	please specify truck payload e.g. 3,5t-7,5t; 7,5t-16t, 16t-32t, >32t	

LCC data inventory

Table 23: LCC data inventory Deodorization KREYEN

CAPEX, OPEX, Revenues					
Type of cost	Cost points	Quantity	Unit	Remarks	Source
<i>Capital costs</i>					
	Buildings/property	176 000	€/m2	59% of PC	own calculations based on (Bashirgonbadi et al., 2022): Expert judgment and (Cimpan et al., 2016; Larrain et al., 2021, 2020; Sinnott and Towler, 2019) Uwe Email 07.09.22
[Price of Equipment (PC)]	Equipment/software	300 000	€/pc.	e.g. machinery	
	Installation and running test (IC)	180 000	€/pc.	60% of PC depreciated on 7 years	
	Engineering and project management (EPMC)	48 000	€/pc.	10% of PC and 10% of IC depreciated on 7 years	
<i>Operational costs</i>					
Personnel	Salary and wages	50 000	€/person.year	assumption_eks: 1.5 person/ktpa	SUEZ
Utility costs	Electricity	0.081	€/ kWh	eks_assumption: EUROSTAT, Europe data (2021)	EUROSTAT
Utility costs	Heat	0.0432	€/ kWh	eks_assumption: EUROSTAT, Europe data (2021)	EUROSTAT
Other operational costs	Maintenance and repairs	28 160	€/year	4% * CAPEX	(Bashirgonbadi et al., 2022): (Cimpan et al., 2016; Larrain et al., 2021)
Other operational costs	Insurance	4 928	€/year	0.7% * CAPEX	(Bashirgonbadi et al., 2022): (Cimpan et al., 2016; Larrain et al., 2021)
Other operational costs	General expenses	13 058	€/year	10% of total operational cost	(Bashirgonbadi et al., 2022): (Cimpan et al., 2016; Larrain et al., 2021)
<i>Revenues/ Positive Cash flows</i>					
Selling of products	Product	n.a	€/ product	Market prices for secondary products	
	Co-product	n.a	€/ product	Market prices for secondary products	
	Subsidies	n.a	€/ year	e.g for setting up a waste recycling mangement system	

S-LCA data inventory

Table 24: S-LCA data inventory Deodorization KREYEN

Indicator	Parameter	Data	KPI
General Information	Total number of employees (FTE)	68	Number of employees per company (FTE)
	Total number of production employee (FTE)	27	Number of employees per company and category (FTE)
	Total number of non-production production employee (FTE)	41	Number of employees per company and category (FTE)
Existence of record of proof of age	Record of proof of age	1000	Number of records per 1000 employees in the company/y
Existence of certified environmental management system (EMS)	EMAS certified EMS exists	no	Category per company/y
	ISO 14001:2015 certified EMS exists	no	Category per company/y
	EMS according to ISO 14001:2015 with internal auditing regime according to ISO 19011:2011 and/or Certified Environmental Management Officer exists Outdated EMS according to ISO 14001:2004 exists	no no	Category per company/y Category per company/y
Percentage of workers who are paid a living wage or above	Number of employees paid in category A Living Wage - Standard family, upper bound per company /y	70	Number of employees per company and category
	Number of employees paid in category B Living Wage - Standard family, lower bound per company /y	0	Number of employees per company and category
	Number of employees paid in category C Living Wage - Single adult, upper bound per company /y	0	Number of employees per company and category
	Number of employees paid in category D Living Wage - Single adult, lower bound per company /y	0	Number of employees per company and category
	Number of employees paid a minimum wage per company /y	0	Number of employees per company and category
Percentage of (fatal and non-fatal) accidents/injuries in the organization	Non-fatal accidents	3	Number of non-fatal accidents per 1000 employees in the company/y
	Fatal accidents	0	Number of fatal accidents per 1000 employees in the company/y
Existence of research and development (R&D)	Research and development department exists	yes	y/n
	Gross profit (GP)	€ 5 000 000	Gross profit (GP)/y
	R&D expenses	€ 300 000	€/ y
Extent of safety training	Average hours of training on occupational health and safety per employee in the company/y	6	h/y and employee
	Total number of training hours for total number of employees	420	Total number of training hours provided to employees
	Total number of training hours for production employees	230	Total number of training hours provided to production employee
	Total number of training hours non-production employees	190	Total number of training hours provided to non-production employee
Existence of health risk assessments regarding toxicity	Health risk assessments regarding toxicity exists	yes	yes/ n.a./ no
Percentage of male/female employees	Male employees	64	Number of employees (FTE)
	Female employees	6	Number of employees (FTE)
	Other employees	0	Number of employees (FTE)
	Not disclosed employees	0	Number of employees (FTE)
	Male full-time employees	64	Number of full-time employees (FTE)
	Female full-time employees	4	Number of full-time employees (FTE)
	Other full-time employees	0	Number of full-time employees (FTE)
	Not disclosed full-time employees	0	Number of full-time employees (FTE)
Existence of extended producer responsibility (EPR) policy	Extended producer responsibility (EPR) policy exists	n.a.	yes/ n.a./ no
Existence of formal policy against discrimination	Formal policy against discrimination exists	no	y/n
	Total number of incidents of discrimination during the reporting period.	0	Number of incidents / reporting period
	Does the formal policy include the following 4 step action plan against discrimination:	no	y/n

Laminate production-AMCOR

LCA data inventory

Loop 1-NF scenario Detergent Tabs (HP2)

Table 25: Loop 1 Detergent Tabs Laminate production data inventory sheet (confidential energy data)

Process 1						
Blown film coextrusion	Inputs	Quantity per m2 of pac	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	PE virgin pellets	0.040	kg			
	PE PCR pellets	0.053	kg			
	PE PCR pellets	0.053	kg			
	PE tie virgin pellets	0.006	kg			
	EVOH virgin pellets *optional	0.003	kg			
	Transport Virgin Plastics	200.000	km		assumption_eks: 200km	
	Transport Virgin Plastics	0.010	tkm		assumption_eks: 16-32t lorry	
	Electricity	confidential	kWh/kg film			confidential
	Electricity	confidential	kWh			
Outputs	Quantity per m2 of pac	Unit	Destination	Remarks	Source	
	BPE film	0.001	kg			
	Virgin PE	9.100	g			
	PCR PE	47.320	g			
	PE tie	2.730	g			
	EVOH	2.280	g			
	PE tie	2.730	g			
	8000/PC	27.000	g			
	Solid losses	0.010	kg		incineration with energy recovery	
99%	PE	0.010	kg			
2%	EVOH	0.000	kg			
	Transport to incineration	30.000	km		assumption_eks: 30 km	Hestin et al 2015
	Transport to incineration	0.000	tkm		assumption_eks: 10t lorry	Hestin et al 2015
Process 2						
Printing	Inputs	Quantity per m2 of pac	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	MDOPE/PCR/25 film	0.025	kg			
	PCR PE	17.694	g/m2			
	PE film	7.583	g/m2			
	Electricity for MDO process	N/A	kWh/m2		still pending	
	Transport Virgin Plastics	200.000	km		assumption_eks: 200km	
	Transport Virgin Plastics	0.005	tkm		assumption_eks: 16-32t lorry	
	Ink	0.002	kg			
	Primer coating	0.002	kg			
	Transport Ink & Primer	291.000	km		assumption_eks: Siegwerk (Wilhelm-Ostwald-Straße 10, 53721 Siegburg, Germany) to Amcor (Obergemesteeweg Zuid 801, 9000 Gent)	
	Transport Ink & Primer	0.001	tkm		assumption_eks: 16-32t lorry	
	Electricity	confidential	kWh		per m2 printed film, 100% full surface print	confidential
	Natural gas	confidential	kWh		per m2 printed film, 100% full surface print	confidential
	Natural gas	confidential	MJ			
	Ethyl acetate	0.007	kg			
	Transport Ethyl Acetate	200.000	km		assumption_eks: 200km	
	Transport Ethyl Acetate	0.001	tkm		assumption_eks: 16-32t lorry	
Outputs	Quantity per m2 of pac	Unit	Destination	Remarks	Source	
	MDOPE/PCR/ink/primer film	1.000	m2			
	MDOPE/PCR/ink/primer film	0.026	kg			
	PCR PE	15.325	g/m2			
	Virgin PE	6.825	g/m2			
	Ink	1.500	g/m2			
	Primer coating	2.000	g/m2			
	Waste Ethyl acetate	0.007	kg		solvent oxidation	
	Solid losses	0.003	kg		incineration with energy recovery	
26.0%	PE	0.001	kg			
13.3%	Ink and primer coating	0.000	kg		assumption_eks: recovered energy from incineration as dirt	
	Transport to incineration	30.000	km		assumption_eks: 30 km	Hestin et al 2015
	Transport to incineration	0.000	tkm		assumption_eks: 10t lorry	Hestin et al 2015
Process 3						
Adhesive lamination	Inputs	Quantity per m2 of pac	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	MDOPE25/ink/primer film	0.026	kg			
	Adhesive SF	0.002	kg		Polyurethane adhesive	
	BPE film	0.091	kg			
	Electricity	confidential	kWh		solvent, duplex	confidential
	Natural gas	confidential	kWh		solvent, duplex	confidential
	Natural gas	confidential	MJ			
	Transport Ethyl Acetate	200.000	km		assumption_eks: 200km	
	Transport Ethyl Acetate	0.000	tkm		assumption_eks: 16-32t lorry	
Outputs	Quantity per m2 of pac	Unit	Destination	Remarks	Source	
	Laminate	1.000	m2			
	Laminate	0.1197	kg			
	MDOPE/PCR/ink/primer film	26.250	g/m2			
	Adhesive SF	2.800	g/m2			
	BPE film	91.460	g/m2			
	Adhesive loss	0.0002	kg		incineration with energy recovery	
	Transport to incineration	30.000	km		assumption_eks: recovered energy from incineration as dirt	
	Transport to incineration	0.000	tkm		assumption_eks: 30 km	Hestin et al 2015
	Transport to incineration	0.000	tkm		assumption_eks: 10t lorry	Hestin et al 2015
Process 4						
Coating	Inputs	Quantity per m2 of pac	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	Laminate	0.120	kg			
	OPV	0.001	kg			
Outputs	Quantity per m2 of pac	Unit	Destination	Remarks	Source	
	Laminate/OPV	0.121	kg			
	OPV	0.001	kg			
Process 2.3.1						
Solvent oxidation with energy recovery	Inputs	Quantity per m2 of pac	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	Waste Ethyl acetate	0.007	kg			
	Electricity	confidential	kWh / kg solvent			confidential
	Natural gas	confidential	kWh / kg solvent			confidential
	Electricity	confidential	kWh			
	Natural gas	confidential	kWh			
	Natural gas	confidential	MJ			
	Oxygen from air	0.011	kg	air	assumption_eks: burden free, from air	
Outputs	Quantity per m2 of pac	Unit	Destination	Remarks	Source	
	Energy (internally used)				included in energy input, hence not included in calculation	
	VOC emissions	0.001	kg	air		
	CO2 emissions	0.012	kg	air	CH4RO2 + 5 O2 = 4 CO2 + 4 H2O - efficiency 85%	
	Water vapor	0.005	kg	air		
Process 5						
Slitting 1&2	Inputs	Quantity per m2 of pac	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	Laminator/OPV	1.000	m2			
	Electricity	confidential	kWh			confidential
Outputs	Quantity per m2 of pac	Unit	Destination	Remarks	Source	
	H2 laminate	1.000	m2			

Loop 2-3 F scenario- Coffee (FP2)

Table 26: Loop 2-3 F scenario- Coffee (FP2) Laminate production data inventory sheet

Process 1						
Blown film coextrusion PCR	Inputs	Quantity per m	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	PE PCR pellets	0.069	kg/m2			
	Electricity	confidential	kWh/kg film			confidential
	Electricity	confidential	kWh/g/m2 (output)			confidential
	Outputs	Quantity per m	Unit	Destination	Remarks	Source
	PE PCR film	0.062	kg/m2			
	solid losses	0.007	kg/m2		Ah: 100% LDPE	
Process 2						
Blown film coextrusion PE-EVOH-PE	Inputs	Quantity per m	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	PE virgin pellets	0.038	kg/m2			
	EVOH virgin pellets	0.003	kg/m2			
	Electricity	confidential	kWh/kg film			confidential
	Electricity	confidential	kWh/g/m2 (output)			confidential
	Outputs	Quantity per m	Unit	Destination	Remarks	Source
	PE-EVOH-PE	0.037	kg/m2			
	EVOH	0.0023				
	PE	0.0346				
	Solid losses	0.0041	kg/m2	incineration with energy recovery	Ah: 95% LDPE, 5% EVOH	
	PE loss	0.0038				
	EVOH loss	0.0003				
Process 3						
Printing	Inputs	Quantity per m	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	OPV-MDOPE-Y-SiOx film	0.024	kg/m2			ask Nicolas
	OPV	0.0011	kg/m2			
	Electricity for OPV coating	confidential	kWh / m2			
	MDOPE-Y-SiOx	0.0202	kg/m2		calculated as the rest (total-OPV and SiOx)	
	Electricity for MDO process	N/A	kWh / m2			
	SiOx coating	0.1111	kg/m2			
	Electricity for SiOx coating	confidential	kWh / m2			
	Ink	0.002	kg/m2			
	Delamination primer	0.001	kg/m2			
	Electricity	confidential	kWh / m2		per m2 printed film, 100% full surface print	confidential
	Natural gas	confidential	kWh / m2		per m2 printed film, 100% full surface print	confidential
	Ethyl acetate	0.004	kg/m2 (Output)		14 g solvent per 4g ink/m2 film	
	Outputs	Quantity per m	Unit	Destination	Remarks	Source
	OPV-MDOPE-Y-SiOx/ink/ primer film	0.022	kg/m2			
	OPV	0.0010	kg/m2			
	MDOPE-Y-SiOx	0.0182	kg/m2			
	Ink	0.0015	kg/m2			
	Delamination primer	0.0010	kg/m2			
	Waste Ethyl acetate	0.004	kg/m2	solvent oxidation		
	Solid losses	0.002	kg/m2	incineration with energy recovery	Ah: 90% LDPE, 10% Dirt	
	OPV	0.0001	kg/m2			
	MDOPE-Y-SiOx	0.0020	kg/m2			
	Ink loss	0.0002	kg/m2			
	Primer loss	0.0001	kg/m2			
Process 4						
Slitting 1	Inputs	Quantity per m	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	OPV-MDOPE-Y-SiOx/ink/ primer film	0.022	kg/m2			
	Electricity	confidential	kWh / m2			confidential
	Outputs	Quantity per m	Unit	Destination	Remarks	Source
	OPV-MDOPE-Y-SiOx/ink/ primer film	0.022	kg/m2			
Process 5						
Slitting 2	Inputs	Quantity per m	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	PE-EVOH-PE	0.037	kg/m2			
	Electricity	confidential	kWh / m2			confidential
	Outputs	Quantity per m	Unit	Destination	Remarks	Source
	PE-EVOH-PE	0.037	kg/m2			
Process 6						
Adhesive lamination 1	Inputs	Quantity per m	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	PE-PCR	0.062	kg/m2			
	Adhesive SF	0.002	kg/m2			
	PE-EVOH-PE	0.037	kg/m2			
	Electricity	confidential	kWh / m2		solvent, duplex	confidential
	Natural gas	confidential	kWh / m2		solvent, duplex	confidential
	Outputs	Quantity per m	Unit	Destination	Remarks	Source
	PE-PCR/adh/PE-EVOH-PE	0.101	kg/m2			
	Solid losses	0.002	kg/m2	incineration with energy recovery		
	Adhesive loss	0.002	kg/m2		Ah: 100% dirt	
Process 7						
Adhesive lamination 2	Inputs	Quantity per m	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	OPV-MDOPE-Y-SiOx/ink/ primer film	0.022	kg/m2			
	Adhesive SF	0.002	kg/m2			
	PE-PCR/adh/PE-EVOH-PE	0.101	kg/m2			
	Electricity	confidential	kWh / m2		solvent, triplex	confidential
	Natural gas	confidential	kWh / m2		solvent, triplex	confidential
	Outputs	Quantity per m	Unit	Destination	Remarks	Source
	Laminate	0.124	kg/m2			
	OPV-MDOPE-Y-SiOx/ink/ primer film	0.0217	kg/m2			
	Adhesive SF	0.0020	kg/m2			
	PE-PCR/adh/PE-EVOH-PE	0.1007	kg/m2			
	Solid losses	0.0002	kg/m2			
	Adhesive loss	0.0002	kg/m2		Ah: 100% dirt	
Process 8						
Solvent oxidation with energy recovery	Inputs	Quantity per m	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	Waste Ethyl acetate	0.004	kg/m2			
	Electricity	confidential	kWh / kg solvent			confidential
	Natural gas	confidential	kWh / kg solvent			confidential
	Electricity	confidential	kWh/m2 (Output)			confidential
	Natural gas	confidential	kWh/m2 (Output)			confidential
	Oxygen from air	0.0054	kg/m2	air		
	Outputs	Quantity per m	Unit	Destination	Remarks	Source
	Energy (internally used)				included in energy input, hence not included in calculation	
	VOC emissions	0.0005	kg/m2	air		
	CO2 emissions	0.0060	kg/m2	air	CH4BO2 + 5 O2 = 4 CO2 + 4 H2O - efficiency 85%	
	Water vapor	0.0024	kg/m2	air	assume burden free (ah)	
Process 9						
Slitting 3	Inputs	Quantity per m	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	Laminate	0.124	kg/m2			
	OPV/MDOPE-Y-SiOx/ink/primer film	0.0217	kg/m2			
	Adhesive SF	0.0020	kg/m2			
	PE-PCR/adh/PE-EVOH-PE	0.1007	kg/m2			
	Electricity	confidential	kWh / m2			confidential
	Outputs	Quantity per m	Unit	Destination	Remarks	Source
	Laminate	0.124	kg/m2			

LCC data inventory

Table 27: LCC data inventory AMCOR, SiOx missing, OPV i.e. heat protective lacquer missing, triplex, duplex differences in price missing

CAPEX, OPEX, Revenues					
Type of cost	Cost points	Quantity	Unit	Remarks	Source
<i>Capital costs</i>					
	Buildings/property	990 614	€/m2 or pc.	own calculation based on ratio SUEZ	
Equipment/software	Unit operation: BLOWN FILM MON AND CO-EXTRUSI	184 261	€/pc.	price for 1 units, depreciated over 15 y	Multicycle
Equipment/software	Unit operation: ADHESIVE SF and SB LAMINATION	401 998	€/pc.	depreciated over 15 y	Multicycle
Equipment/software	Unit operation: DIGITAL PRINTING (NTC)	24 151	€/pc.	depreciated over 15 y	Multicycle
Equipment/software	Unit operation: SLITTING	50 000	€/pc.	€ 24 151	https://havesino.en.made-in-china.com (2023)
	Equipment installation	396 246	€		Perry's Chemical Engineers' Handbook
	Piping	132 082	€		Perry's Chemical Engineers' Handbook
	Instrumentation	132 082	€		Perry's Chemical Engineers' Handbook
	Electrical	99 061	€		Perry's Chemical Engineers' Handbook
	Buildings, process	66 041	€		Perry's Chemical Engineers' Handbook
	Design and engineering	297 184	€		Perry's Chemical Engineers' Handbook
	Contingency	148 592	€		Perry's Chemical Engineers' Handbook
<i>Operational costs</i>					
Personnel	Salary and wages	48 000	€/person.year	BE average, Chemical Engineer Salaries	https://www.stepstone.be/salaris/Chemisch-ingenieur.html
	Labour use	22	FTE/capacity	Tech.)	Multicycle
	Labour use	2	FTE/ktpa		Multicycle
Intermediate goods	rPE (IVV) - High	1 500	€/ t		IVV
	vPE	1 850	€/ t	POLYMERPREISE – Kunststoff Information (kiweb.de)	Multicycle
	vEVOH	4 300	€/ t	https://www.made-in-china.com/products-search/hot-china-products/Evoh_Price.html	
	Ethyl acetate	995	€/ t	Ethyl Acetate at Best Price in India (indiamart.com)	Multicycle
	Nitrocellulose/PU Ink	1 200	€/ t		Multicycle, update ask SIEGWERK
	Primer	9 000	€/ t		Siegwerk
	Tracer	confidential	€/kg		POLY
	Adhesive	1 200	€/ t	assumption_eks: similar to ink	Siegwerk
	Solvent	3	€/ l		Multicycle
Utility costs	Diesel	1	€/ l		Multicycle
	Fuel oil	2	€/ kg		Multicycle
Freshwater	Chilling water	0.06	€/ t		Multicycle
	Cooling water	0.05	€/ t		Multicycle
Electricity	Electricity	0.20	€/ kWh	EUROSTAT, 2022 data EU	EUROSTAT
Heat	Natural gas	0.06	€/ kWh	EUROSTAT, 2022 data EU	EUROSTAT
	Steam	12	€/ t		Multicycle
Other	Nitrogen	0.05	€/ Sm ³		Multicycle
	Waste treatment	0.06	€/ m ³		Multicycle
Other operational costs	Maintenance and repairs	77 268	€/year	4% * CAPEX	(Bashirgonbadi et al., 2022); (Cimpan et al., 2016; Larrain et al., 2021)
Other operational costs	Insurance	13 522	€/year	0.7% * CAPEX	(Bashirgonbadi et al., 2022); (Cimpan et al., 2016; Larrain et al., 2021)
<i>Revenues/ Positive Cash flows</i>					
Selling of products	Product duplex detergent tabs laminate	0.75	€/ m2	general market price, higher price for new structure	AMCOR
	Product triplex coffee powder laminate	0.80	€/ m2	general market price, higher price for new structure	AMCOR

S-LCA data inventory

Table 28: S-LCA data inventory AMCORG = AMCOR Ghent, safety training numbers to be updated, N/A not available, n.a. not applicable

Indicator	Parameter	Data	KPI
General Information	Total number of employees (FTE)	434	Number of employees per company (FTE)
	Total number of production employee (FTE)	208	Number of employees per company and category (FTE)
	Total number of non-production production employee (FTE)	226	Number of employees per company and category (FTE)
Existence of record of proof of age	Record of proof of age	454	Number of records per 1000 employees in the company/y
Existence of certified environmental management system (EMS)	EMAS certified EMS exists	no	Category per company/y
	ISO 14001:2015 certified EMS exists	yes	Category per company/y
	EMS according to ISO 14001:2015 with internal auditing regime according to ISO 19011:2011 and/or Certified Environmental Management Officer exists	yes	Category per company/y
	Outdated EMS according to ISO 14001:2004 exists	no	Category per company/y
	Number of employees paid in category A Living Wage - Standard family, upper bound per company /y	454	Number of employees per company and category
	Number of employees paid in category B Living Wage - Standard family, lower bound per company /y	0	Number of employees per company and category
	Number of employees paid in category C Living Wage - Single adult, upper bound per company /y	0	Number of employees per company and category
	Number of employees paid in category D Living Wage - Single adult, lower bound per company /y	0	Number of employees per company and category
	Number of employees paid a minimum wage per company /y	0	Number of employees per company and category
Percentage of (fatal and non-fatal) accidents/injuries in the organization	Non-fatal accidents	0	Number of non-fatal accidents per 1000 employees in the company/y
	Fatal accidents	0	Number of fatal accidents per 1000 employees in the company/y
Existence of research and development (R&D)	Research and development department exists	no	y/n
	Gross profit (GP)	N/A	Gross profit (GP)/y
	R&D expenses	N/A	€/ y
Extent of safety training	Average hours of training on occupational health and safety per employee in the company/y	6.4	h/y and employee
	Total number of training hours for total number of employees	4495	Total number of training hours provided to employees
	Total number of training hours for production employees	3259	Total number of training hours provided to production employee
	Total number of training hours non-production employees	1236	Total number of training hours provided to non-production employee
Existence of health risk assessments regarding toxicity	Health risk assessments regarding toxicity exists	yes	yes/ n.a./ no
Percentage of male/female employees	Male employees	388	Number of employees (FTE)
	Female employees	56	Number of employees (FTE)
	Other employees	0	Number of employees (FTE)
	Not disclosed employees	0	Number of employees (FTE)
	Male full-time employees	0	Number of full-time employees (FTE)
	Female full-time employees	0	Number of full-time employees (FTE)
	Other full-time employees	0	Number of full-time employees (FTE)
	Not disclosed full-time employees	0	Number of full-time employees (FTE)
Existence of extended producer responsibility (EPR) policy	Extended producer responsibility (EPR) policy exists	yes	yes/ n.a./ no
Existence of formal policy against discrimination	Formal policy against discrimination exists	yes	y/n
	Total number of incidents of discrimination during the reporting period.	0	Number of incidents / reporting period
	Does the formal policy include the following 4 step action plan against discrimination:	yes	y/n

Table 29: S-LCA data inventory AMCORK, = AMCOR Kreuzlingen, non-fatal accidents to be clarified

Indicator	Parameter	Data	KPI
General Information	Total number of employees (FTE)	388	Number of employees per company (FTE)
	Total number of production employee (FTE)	189	Number of employees per company and category (FTE)
	Total number of non-production production employee (FTE)	199	Number of employees per company and category (FTE)
Existence of record of proof of age	Record of proof of age	388	Number of records per 1000 employees in the company/y
Existence of certified environmental management system (EMS)	EMAS certified EMS exists	yes	Category per company/y
	ISO 14001:2015 certified EMS exists	no	Category per company/y
	EMS according to ISO 14001:2015 with internal auditing regime according to ISO 19011:2011 and/or Certified Environmental Management Officer exists	no	Category per company/y
	Outdated EMS according to ISO 14001:2004 exists	no	Category per company/y
	Number of employees paid in category A Living Wage - Standard family, upper bound per company /y	200	Number of employees per company and category
	Number of employees paid in category B Living Wage - Standard family, lower bound per company /y	0	Number of employees per company and category
	Number of employees paid in category C Living Wage - Single adult, upper bound per company /y	188	Number of employees per company and category
	Number of employees paid in category D Living Wage - Single adult, lower bound per company /y	0	Number of employees per company and category
	Number of employees paid a minimum wage per company /y	0	Number of employees per company and category
Percentage of (fatal and non-fatal) accidents/injuries in the organization	Non-fatal accidents	0.0103	Number of non-fatal accidents per 1000 employees in the company/y
	Fatal accidents	0	Number of fatal accidents per 1000 employees in the company/y
Existence of research and development (R&D)	Research and development department exists	yes	y/n
	Gross profit (GP)	N/A	Gross profit (GP)/y
	R&D expenses	N/A	€/ y
Extent of safety training	Average hours of training on occupational health and safety per employee in the company/y	20.0	h/y and employee
	Total number of training hours for total number of employees	7500	Total number of training hours provided to employees
	Total number of training hours for production employees	3500	Total number of training hours provided to production employee
	Total number of training hours non-production employees	4000	Total number of training hours provided to non-production employee
Existence of health risk assessments regarding toxicity	Health risk assessments regarding toxicity exists	yes	yes/ n.a./ no
Percentage of male/female employees	Male employees	329	Number of employees (FTE)
	Female employees	59	Number of employees (FTE)
	Other employees	0	Number of employees (FTE)
	Not disclosed employees	0	Number of employees (FTE)
	Male full-time employees	328	Number of full-time employees (FTE)
	Female full-time employees	40	Number of full-time employees (FTE)
	Other full-time employees	0	Number of full-time employees (FTE)
	Not disclosed full-time employees	0	Number of full-time employees (FTE)
Existence of extended producer responsibility (EPR) policy	Extended producer responsibility (EPR) policy exists	yes	yes/ n.a./ no
Existence of formal policy against discrimination	Formal policy against discrimination exists	yes	y/n
	Total number of incidents of discrimination during the reporting period.	0	Number of incidents / reporting period
	Does the formal policy include the following 4 step action plan against discrimination:	yes	y/n

Tracer production-POLY

LCA data inventory

Loop 3

The LCA data inventory for Tracer production-POLY is considered confidential and is shared exclusively within the project consortium.

LCC data inventory

The LCC data inventory for Tracer production-POLY is shared within the project consortium. The investment cost for a TBSLight upgrade is generally publicly available. However, the current policy is to offer the installation of the upgrade for free, depending on the customer's commitment to a long-term business relationship. This initiative aims to broaden the market outreach. Consequently, it is preferable to communicate this offering rather than specifying a monetary value.

S-LCA data inventory

Table 30: S-LCA data inventory POLY

Indicator	Parameter	Data	KPI
General Information	Total number of employees (FTE)	30	Number of employees per company (FTE)
	Total number of production employee (FTE)	7.5	Number of employees per company and category (FTE)
	Total number of non-production production employee (FTE)	23	Number of employees per company and category (FTE)
Existence of record of proof of age	Record of proof of age	32	Number of records per 1000 employees in the company/y
Existence of certified environmental management system (EMS)	EMAS certified EMS exists	no	Category per company/y
	ISO 14001:2015 certified EMS exists	yes	Category per company/y
	EMS according to ISO 14001:2015 with internal auditing regime according to ISO 19011:2011 and/or Certified Environmental Management Officer exists	no	Category per company/y
	Outdated EMS according to ISO 14001:2004 exists	no	Category per company/y
Percentage of (fatal and non-fatal) accidents/injuries in the organization	Number of employees paid in category A Living Wage - Standard family, upper bound per company /y	32	Number of employees per company and category
	Number of employees paid in category B Living Wage - Standard family, lower bound per company /y	0	Number of employees per company and category
	Number of employees paid in category C Living Wage - Single adult, upper bound per company /y	0	Number of employees per company and category
	Number of employees paid in category D Living Wage - Single adult, lower bound per company /y	0	Number of employees per company and category
	Number of employees paid a minimum wage per company /y	0	Number of employees per company and category
Existence of research and development (R&D)	Research and development department exists	yes	y/n
	Gross profit (GP)	confidential	Gross profit (GP)/y
Extent of safety training	R&D expenses	confidential	€/ y
	Average hours of training on occupational health and safety per employee in the company/y	8	h/y and employee
	Total number of training hours for total number of employees	16	Total number of training hours provided to employees
	Total number of training hours for production employees	12.6	Total number of training hours provided to production employee
Existence of health risk assessments regarding toxicity	Total number of training hours non-production employees	3.2	Total number of training hours provided to non-production employee
	Health risk assessments regarding toxicity exists	yes	yes/ n.a. / no
Percentage of male/female employees	Extended producer responsibility (EPR) policy exists	n.a.	yes/ n.a. / no
	Male employees	26	Number of employees (FTE)
	Female employees	6	Number of employees (FTE)
	Other employees	0	Number of employees (FTE)
	Not disclosed employees	0	Number of employees (FTE)
	Male full-time employees	21	Number of full-time employees (FTE)
	Female full-time employees	2	Number of full-time employees (FTE)
	Other full-time employees	0	Number of full-time employees (FTE)
Existence of formal policy against discrimination	Not disclosed full-time employees	0	Number of full-time employees (FTE)
	Formal policy against discrimination exists	no	y/n
Existence of extended producer responsibility (EPR) policy	Formal policy against discrimination exists	no	y/n
	Total number of incidents of discrimination during the reporting period.	0	Number of incidents / reporting period
	Does the formal policy include the following 4 step action plan against discrimination:	no	y/n

Ink, Primer and heat protective lacquer production-Siegwerk

LCA data inventory

Loop 1-2 Ink

Table 31: Loop 1-2 Ink CMYK production data inventory sheet; K: black

Process 1						
Dispersion	Inputs	Quantity per kg	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	Polyurethan	0.240	kg		Binding agent	
	Pigment Cor M or Y or K	0.060	kg			
	Additives	0.030	kg			
	Ethanol	0.335	kg		Bioethanol	
	Ethylacetat	0.335	kg			
	Electricity	0.035	kWh		For a colorless varnish and generally mixing operations we calculate with an average value of 35kwh/t	
Outputs	Quantity per kg	Unit	Destination	Remarks	Source	
Dispersion		1	kg			
Process 2						
Blending	Inputs	Quantity per kg	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	Dispersion		1	kg		
	Electricity	0.16	kWh		For a pigmented mastergrind we calculate with an average value 160kwh/t	
Outputs	Quantity per kg	Unit	Destination	Remarks	Source	
Ink		1	kg			
Transport (T)						
T1	Inputs	Transport mode	Unit	Truck technology	Remarks	Source
		Lorry	km	EURO 6	please specify truck payload e.g. 3,5t-7,5t; 7,5t-16t, 16t-32t, >32t	
T2	Inputs	Transport mode	Unit	Truck technology	Remarks	Source
		Lorry	km	EURO 6	please specify truck payload e.g. 3,5t-7,5t; 7,5t-16t, 16t-32t, >32t	

Table 32: Loops 1-2 Ink white production data inventory sheet

Process 1						
Dispersion	Inputs	Quantity per kg	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	Polyurethan	0.22	kg		Binding agent	
	Titanoxid	0.25	kg		Pigment	
	Additives	0.03	kg			
	Ethanol	0.25	kg		Bioethanol	
	Ethylacetat	0.25	kg			
	Electricity	0.035	kWh			
Outputs	Quantity per kg	Unit	Destination	Remarks	Source	
Dispersion		1	kg			
Process 2						
Blending	Inputs	Quantity per kg	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	Dispersion		1	kg		
	Electricity	0.16	kWh			
Outputs	Quantity per kg	Unit	Destination	Remarks	Source	
Ink		1	kg			
Transport (T)						
T1	Inputs	Transport mode	Unit	Truck technology	Remarks	Source
		Lorry	km	EURO 6	please specify truck payload e.g. 3,5t-7,5t; 7,5t-16t, 16t-32t, >32t	
T2	Inputs	Transport mode	Unit	Truck technology	Remarks	Source
		Lorry	km	EURO 6	please specify truck payload e.g. 3,5t-7,5t; 7,5t-16t, 16t-32t, >32t	

Loop 3 Ink+Tracer

Table 33: Loop 3 Ink CMYK production data inventory sheet, data on tracer is confidential, K= black

Process 1						
Dispersion	Inputs	Quantity per kg	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	Polyurethan	0.240	kg		Binding agent	
	Pigment Cor M or Y or K	0.060	kg			
	Additives	0.030	kg			
	Ethanol	0.335	kg		Bioethanol	
	Ethylacetat	0.335	kg			
	Tracer	confidential	kg			
	Electricity	0.035	kWh		For a colorless varnish and generally mixing operations we calculate with an average value of 35kwh/t	
Outputs	Quantity per kg	Unit	Destination	Remarks	Source	
Dispersion	1	kg				
Process 2						
Blending	Inputs	Quantity per kg	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	Dispersion	1	kg			
	Electricity	0.16	kWh		For a pigmented mastergrind we calculate with an average value 160kwh/t	
Outputs	Quantity per kg	Unit	Destination	Remarks	Source	
Ink	1	kg				
Transport (T)						
T1	Inputs	Transport mode	Unit	Truck technology	Remarks	Source
		Lorry	km	EURO 6	please specify truck payload e.g. 3,5t-7,5t; 7,5t-16t, 16t-32t, >32t	
T2	Inputs	Transport mode	Unit	Truck technology	Remarks	Source
		Lorry	km	EURO 6	please specify truck payload e.g. 3,5t-7,5t; 7,5t-16t, 16t-32t, >32t	

Table 34: Loop 3 Ink + tracer white production data inventory sheet, data on tracer is confidential

Process 1						
Dispersion	Inputs	Quantity per kg	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	Polyurethan	0.22	kg		Binding agent	
	Titanoxid	0.25	kg		Pigment	
	Additives	0.03	kg			
	Ethanol	0.25	kg		Bioethanol	
	Ethylacetat	0.25	kg			
	Electricity	0.035	kWh			
	Tracer	confidential	kg			
Outputs	Quantity per kg	Unit	Destination	Remarks	Source	
Dispersion	1	kg				
Process 2						
Blending	Inputs	Quantity per kg	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	Dispersion	1	kg			
	Electricity	0.16	kWh			
Outputs	Quantity per kg	Unit	Destination	Remarks	Source	
Ink	1	kg				
Transport (T)						
T1	Inputs	Transport mode	Unit	Truck technology	Remarks	Source
		Lorry	km	EURO 6	please specify truck payload e.g. 3,5t-7,5t; 7,5t-16t, 16t-32t, >32t	
T2	Inputs	Transport mode	Unit	Truck technology	Remarks	Source
		Lorry	km	EURO 6	please specify truck payload e.g. 3,5t-7,5t; 7,5t-16t, 16t-32t, >32t	

Loop 2-3 Primer

Table 35: Loop 2-3 Primer production data inventory sheet

Process 1						
Blending	Inputs	Quantity per kg	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	Acrylate resin	0.35	kg			
	Water	0.65	kg			
	Electricity	0.0350	kWh			
Outputs	Quantity per kg	Unit	Destination	Remarks	Source	
Primer	1	kg				
Transport (T)						
T1	Inputs	Transport mode	Unit	Truck technology	Remarks	Source
		Lorry	km	EURO 6	please specify truck payload e.g. 3,5t-7,5t; 7,5t-16t, 16t-32t, >32t	
T2	Inputs	Transport mode	Unit	Truck technology	Remarks	Source
		Lorry	km	EURO 6	please specify truck payload e.g. 3,5t-7,5t; 7,5t-16t, 16t-32t, >32t	

Loop 1-3 Heat protective lacquer

Table 36: Loop -3 Heat protective lacquer inventory sheet

Process 1						
Blending	Inputs	Quantity per kg	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
Bindemittel	Polyvinylbutyral	265	g			
	Additives	75	g		Slip agent, waxes, polyesters, stabilizers etc. (would simply take polyester for the LCA)	
	Electricity	0.0350	kWh			
organic solvents	Ethylacetat	660	g			
Outputs						
	Quantity per kg	Unit	Destination	Remarks	Source	
	Heat protective lacquer	1 000	g			
Transport (T)						
T1	Inputs	Transport mode	Unit	Truck technology	Remarks	Source
		Lorry	km	EURO 6	please specify truck payload e.g. 3,5t- 7,5t; 7,5t-16t, 16t-32t, >32t	

LCC data inventory

The LCC data inventory i.e. prices for Ink, Primer and Heat protective lacquer are included in the foreground LCC data inventory of the laminate production by AMCOR.

S-LCA data inventory

Table 37: S-LCA data inventory Siegwerk

Indicator	Parameter	Data	KPI
General Information	Total number of employees (FTE)	920	Number of employees per company (FTE)
	Total number of production employee (FTE)	343	Number of employees per company and category (FTE)
	Total number of non-production production employee (FTE)	577	Number of employees per company and category (FTE)
Existence of record of proof of age (no child labor)	Record of proof of age	989	Number of records per 1000 employees in the company/y
Existence of certified environmental management system (EMS)	EMAS certified EMS exists	yes	Category per company/y
	ISO 14001:2015 certified EMS exists	yes	Category per company/y
	EMS according to ISO 14001:2015 with internal auditing regime according to ISO 19011:2011 and/or Certified Environmental Management Officer exists	yes	Category per company/y
	Outdated EMS according to ISO 14001:2004 exists	no	Category per company/y
	Number of employees paid in category A Living Wage - Standard family, upper bound per company /y	989	Number of employees per company and category
	Number of employees paid in category B Living Wage - Standard family, lower bound per company /y	0	Number of employees per company and category
	Number of employees paid in category C Living Wage - Single adult, upper bound per company /y	0	Number of employees per company and category
	Number of employees paid in category D Living Wage - Single adult, lower bound per company /y	0	Number of employees per company and category
	Number of employees paid a minimum wage per company /y	0	Number of employees per company and category
Percentage of (fatal and non-fatal) accidents/injuries in the organization	Non-fatal accidents	30.43	Number of non-fatal accidents per 1000 employees in the company/y
	Fatal accidents	0	Number of fatal accidents per 1000 employees in the company/y
Existence of research and development (R&D)	Research and development department exists	yes	y/n
	Gross profit (GP)	confidential	Gross profit (GP)/y
	R&D expenses	€ 5 300 000	€/ y
Extent of safety training	Average hours of training on occupational health and safety per employee in the company/y	10	h/y and employee
	Total number of training hours for total number of employees	9200	Total number of training hours provided to employees
	Total number of training hours for production employees	5831	Total number of training hours provided to production employee
	Total number of training hours non-production employees	3369	Total number of training hours provided to non-production employee
Existence of health risk assessments regarding toxicity	Health risk assessments regarding toxicity exists	yes	yes/ n.a./ no
Percentage of male/female employees	Male employees	733	Number of employees (FTE)
	Female employees	187	Number of employees (FTE)
	Other employees	0	Number of employees (FTE)
	Not disclosed employees	0	Number of employees (FTE)
	Male full-time employees	704	Number of full-time employees (FTE)
	Female full-time employees	117	Number of full-time employees (FTE)
	Other full-time employees	0	Number of full-time employees (FTE)
	Not disclosed full-time employees	0	Number of full-time employees (FTE)
Existence of extended producer responsibility (EPR) policy	Extended producer responsibility (EPR) policy exists	n.a.	yes/ n.a./ no
Existence of formal policy against discrimination	Formal policy against discrimination exists	yes	y/n
	Total number of incidents of discrimination during the reporting period.	0	Number of incidents / reporting period
	Does the formal policy include the following 4 step action plan against discrimination:	yes	y/n

Food and non-food packaging production-Nestle/Mespack

LCA data inventory

Loop 1 - 3

Table 38: Loop 2-3 Food packaging production data inventory sheet, tbd: to be disclosed, N/A not applicable, losses are not evaluated per step but at the beginning included in the folding process

Process 1						
Folding	Inputs	Quantity per ton	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	Food Laminate in shape of reets	1	ton			
	Electricity	110	kWh			
	Energy use	135	MJ			
	Compressed Air	N/A	m3			
	Outputs	Quantity per ton	Unit	Destination	Remarks	Source
	Folded Food Laminate	0.95	ton			
	Solid Losses	0.05	ton			
Process 2						
Vertical sealing	Inputs	Quantity per ton	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	Folded Food Laminate	0.95	ton			
	Electricity	110	kWh			
	Compressed Air	N/A	m3			
	Energy use	135	MJ			
	Outputs	Quantity per ton	Unit	Destination	Remarks	Source
	Vertically sealed Food Laminate	0.95	ton			
Process 3						
Bottom sealing	Inputs	Quantity per ton	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	Vertically sealed Food Laminate	0.95	ton			
	Electricity	110	kWh			
	Energy use	135	MJ			
	Compressed Air	N/A	m3			
	Outputs	Quantity per ton	Unit	Destination	Remarks	Source
	Vertically & Bottom Sealed Food Laminate	0.95	ton			
	Solid Losses	N/A	ton		included in losses of folding	
Process 4						
Cutting	Inputs	Quantity per ton	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	Vertically & Bottom Sealed Food Laminate	0.95	ton			
	Electricity	110	kWh			
	Energy use	135	MJ			
	Compressed Air	N/A	m3			
	Outputs	Quantity per ton	Unit	Destination	Remarks	Source
	Cut-out Food Laminate	0.95	ton		filling	
	Solid Losses	N/A	ton		included in losses of folding	
Process 5						
Top sealing	Inputs	Quantity per ton	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	Filled Food Laminate	0.95	ton		assumption ah: no losses during filling	
	Electricity	110	kWh			
	Energy use	135	MJ			
	Compressed Air	N/A	m3			
	Outputs	Quantity per ton	Unit	Destination	Remarks	Source
	Primary Packed, filled laminate sachet	0.95	ton			
	Solid Losses	N/A	ton		included in losses of folding	
Process 6						
Packing and storing	Inputs	Quantity per ton	Unit	Origin	Remarks	Source
	Primary Packed, filled laminate sachet	0.95	ton			
	Electricity	110	kWh			
	Energy use	135	MJ			
	Compressed Air	N/A	m3			
	Secondary/ Tertiary Packaging	tbd	ton			
	Outputs	Quantity per ton	Unit	Destination	Remarks	Source
	Tertiary Packed, filled laminate sachet	0.950	ton			
	Solid Losses	N/A	ton		included in losses of folding	
Transport (T)						
T1	Inputs	Transport mode	Unit	Truck technology	Remarks	Source
	Tertiary Packed, filled laminate sachet	Lorry	km	EURO 6	please specify truck payload e.g. 3,5t-7,5t; 7,5t-16t, 16t-32t, >32t	

LCC data inventory

The LCC data inventory is pending.

S-LCA data inventory

Table 39: S-LCA data inventory NESTLÉ

Indicator	Parameter	Data	KPI
General Information	Total number of employees (FTE)	91	Number of employees per company (FTE)
	Total number of production employee (FTE)	67	Number of employees per company and category (FTE)
	Total number of non-production production employee (FTE)	24	Number of employees per company and category (FTE)
Existence of record of proof of age	Record of proof of age	1000	Number of records per 1000 employees in the company/y
Existence of certified environmental management system (EMS)	EMAS certified EMS exists	yes	Category per company/y
	ISO 14001:2015 certified EMS exists	yes	Category per company/y
	EMS according to ISO 14001:2015 with internal auditing regime according to ISO 19011:2011 and/or Certified Environmental Management Officer exists	yes	Category per company/y
	Outdated EMS according to ISO 14001:2004 exists	no	Category per company/y
	Number of employees paid in category A Living Wage - Standard family, upper bound per company /y	20000	Number of employees per company and category
	Number of employees paid in category B Living Wage - Standard family, lower bound per company /y	0	Number of employees per company and category
	Number of employees paid in category C Living Wage - Single adult, upper bound per company /y	0	Number of employees per company and category
	Number of employees paid in category D Living Wage - Single adult, lower bound per company /y	0	Number of employees per company and category
	Number of employees paid a minimum wage per company /y	0	Number of employees per company and category
Percentage of (fatal and non-fatal) accidents/injuries in the organization	Non-fatal accidents	0	Number of non-fatal accidents per 1000 employees in the company/y
	Fatal accidents	0	Number of fatal accidents per 1000 employees in the company/y
Existence of research and development (R&D)	Research and development department exists	yes	y/n
	Gross profit (GP)	€ 42 700 000 000	Gross profit (GP)/y
	R&D expenses	€ 1 700 000 000	€/ y
Extent of safety training	Average hours of training on occupational health and safety per employee in the company/y	9	h/y and employee
	Total number of training hours for total number of employees	4131	Total number of training hours provided to employees
	Total number of training hours for production employees	1980	Total number of training hours provided to production employee
	Total number of training hours non-production employees	2151	Total number of training hours provided to non-production employee
Existence of health risk assessments regarding toxicity	Health risk assessments regarding toxicity exists	yes	yes/ n.a./ no
Percentage of male/female employees	Male employees	62	Number of employees (FTE)
	Female employees	29	Number of employees (FTE)
	Other employees	0	Number of employees (FTE)
	Not disclosed employees	0	Number of employees (FTE)
	Male full-time employees	62	Number of full-time employees (FTE)
	Female full-time employees	29	Number of full-time employees (FTE)
	Other full-time employees	0	Number of full-time employees (FTE)
	Not disclosed full-time employees	0	Number of full-time employees (FTE)
Existence of extended producer responsibility (EPR) policy	Extended producer responsibility (EPR) policy exists	yes	yes/ n.a./ no
Existence of formal policy against discrimination	Formal policy against discrimination exists	yes	y/n
	Total number of incidents of discrimination during the reporting period.	0	Number of incidents / reporting period
	Does the formal policy include the following 4 step action plan against discrimination:	yes	y/n

